

Developing a prompt protocol suite for scaffolding Complex Thinking with LLM tools: Challenges and solutions

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Abstract

This paper reports an exploratory study exploring the interaction of a theoretical framework for Complex Thinking and AI (LLMs), in terms of its potentialities and constraints. We develop and conduct a preliminary pilot evaluation of a tool comprised of a prompt protocol suite for use with an LLM, to scaffold Complex Thinking of an individual or group in relation to a given Target System of Interest (i.e. a real-world system, a problem, a concern), with the goal of developing more complex understandings of such systems that could guide more effective and positive actions and decisions. We describe the process of developing a suite of prompt protocols for scaffolding particular properties of Complex Thinking and report on the outcomes of a pilot test evaluation with a set of users across different domains.

1. Introduction

1.1 Complex challenges requiring complex responses

Current global challenges have highlighted the inadequacy of the dominant modes of human thinking and the decision-making processes that address complex problems (Rogers et al., 2013; Wells, 2013; Mancilla García et al., 2020). Worldwide, multiple risk processes interact, at various scales and levels, in complex ways, driving social and ecological crises, with, oftentimes, unexpected but profound impacts on the lives of individuals and communities both locally and globally (Renn, 2017). The pressure to change our dominant stances and modes of thinking and to embrace the complexity of the challenges at hand is bigger than ever (Morin, 2005/1990). It has been proposed that the modes of thinking underlying decision-making and action in relation to complex systems (e.g. interventions in social-ecological systems), need to be commensurately congruent and hold as much variety as the systems they are trying to understand and affect (Caves & Melo, 2018; Ashby, 1958). Guiding principles have been formulated inspired by knowledge on the organisation of complex systems, namely living and adaptive systems (Morin, 2005/1990, 2014). There has been a growing recognition of the need to train and educate for complexity and to develop ways of operationalising some of those principles (Morin, 2002; Ramírez-Montoya et al., 2001). Building from research on complex biological and social systems and on the proposal of Edgar Morin, Melo (2020) presented a theoretical framework to support the practice of Complex Thinking (CT). The notion of CT is not simply defined, as there are a variety of definitions and perspectives circulating in the literature which refer as much to the contents as to the processes of thinking (Melo et al., 2020). More recently, there has been a growing interest in CT defined as a kind of higher-order thinking or as a core meta-competence, of critical importance for the XXI century (Ramírez-Montoya, et al., 2021). While some of these authors refer to Morin's thinking, most equate CT with the integration or combination of meta-cognitive capacities, critical thinking, creative thinking and systemic thinking (Baena-Rojas, Ramírez-Montoya, Mazo-Cuervo, & López-Caudana, 2022; Ramírez-Montoya, et al., 2021; Ramírez-Montoya et al., 2022; Silva Pacheco & Iturra Herrera, 2021), as well as reflexivity (Morales, 2020). In this alignment, more studies are emerging regarding interventions to promote these skills (Ramírez-Montoya, et al., 2021; Olivo-Montaño et al., 2024), namely those that explore the use of technologies (Patiño, Ramírez-Montoya & Ibarra-Vazquez, 2023), particularly in the context of higher-education, where attempts have also been made to develop evaluation scales (Tobón & Luna-Nemecio, 2021).

In the framework proposed by Melo (2020), CT is grounded in a relational ontology and a view of cognition as embodied and enacted (Varela, Thompson, Rosh, 2016). It conceptualises both a process and an outcome of the coupling between a given Observer and their environment (mutually defined). As a process, CT attends to and recognises properties of complex systems but also enacts them, in its own organisation, thereby performing complexity (e.g. leading to novel,

surprising emergent ideas or possibilities for action). The more complex the thinking, as an outcome, the more it (i) affords a multiplicity of descriptions, explanations and anticipations, (ii) leads to emergent knowledge information that increases the coherence of the coupling between the observer and their targets of interest; (iii) expands the possibilities for effective actions for promoting, supporting or managing changes, leading to more positive results from the perspective of the widest variety of critical observers in a system and (iv) supports constructive interactions amongst them and their positive co-evolution (Melo, 2020). The proposed framework lists 9 dimensions along with a set of 24 corresponding properties characterising the practice and outcomes of CT: structural complexity (structural variety and dimensionality, relationality); dynamic/process complexity (recursiveness, dynamic processes, relativity/ambiguity/uncertainty); causal and explanatory complexity (modes and finalities, historicity, complex circularity, emergence); dialogic complexity (dualities and complementary pairs; trinities); observers' complexity (multipositionality, reflexivity, intentionalities), developmental and adaptive complexity (developmental-adaptive value, developmental evolvability); pragmatic complexity (pragmatic value, pragmatic sustainability); ethical (ethical value) and aesthetical complexity (aesthetical value) and narrative complexity (differentiation and integration, identities, flexibility/openness). A more recent revision of the model (Melo & Renault, in preparation), stimulated by the constraints of operationalising CT in the context of this study, assumes some dimensions as central (structural, dynamical, causal/explanatory and dialogic complexity), in particular the structural dimension, which generates the contents of the thinking and others as modulating properties (observer, developmental/adaptive, pragmatic, ethical/aesthetical, and narrative complexity), which shape and fine tune the performance of the central properties, ensuring the fitness of the thinking to the social and environmental conditions of the context at stake.

Although these properties, conceived as *thinking movements*, can be executed in isolation, with different levels of complexity, CT requires the coordination and interaction between them for the creation of conditions for the emergence of abductive and emergent leaps which generate novel and meaningful information, for a particular context. This information may guide the observer's actions and decision-making, in relation to their Target Systems of Interest (TSoI) (SEBoK, 2024; The Open University, 2023) in ecosystemically fit and effective ways. CT can also be seen as the contributions of an observer for a complex coupling (or dance) with their environments characterised by the unfolding of different dynamic configurations of properties through time (Melo & Renault, 2024). These configurations can be more or less capable of leading to creative and abductive leaps and to the emergence of new and relevant information.

It is critical to have theoretical frameworks on CT informing the development of tools and strategies to support decision making and actions in response to complex problems. Such tools should guide the enactment of the principles of CT to expand, augment and expand our individual and collective intelligences and cognitive capacities.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is often presented as a potentially powerful route to address complex challenges and to finding adequate responses aiming at a wider "social good" (Manyika, 2022). As stated by Cowls and collaborators (Cowls et al., 2021, p. 114) "designed well, AI technologies can foster the delivery of socially good outcomes with unprecedented scale and efficiency". Recent advances in AI opened the possibility of managing large amounts of information, in ways that may contribute to building complex knowledge. There are, however, other possibilities for dealing with complex problems, namely to use AI systems to promote more complex modes of thinking in humans, or to assemble hybrid systems of collective intelligences (Cui & Yasseri, 2024; Hemmer et al., 2021; Jarrahi et al., 2022; Kamar, 2016) capable of performing it.

1.2 Scaffolding Complex Thinking and Artificial Intelligence

The notion of Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), as proposed by Vygotsky (Vygotsky & Cole, 1978), entailing a relational ontology (Stetsenko, 2017), refers to the idea that we can exercise cognitive capacities that are beyond our usual performance when in the context of a relation with a more competent other, that scaffolds our performance. The scaffolding is, hence, a process that assists a given entity in achieving a performance that they would otherwise not achieve independently. The re-visitation of this zone may lead to an expansion of that entity's capacities to the point where they are transformed and a new ZPD is created.

Recent advances in the domain of Artificial Intelligence have offered opportunities for assembling systems of collective intelligence (Cui & Yasseri, 2024) which expand the possibilities for thinking and possibility thinking (Beghetto, 2023). While a deeper understanding of cognitive processes can contribute to the development of more sophisticated forms of AI (Marcus & Davis, 2021) current tools may already have the potential to operate as minimally effective "partners in cognition" (Solomon, Perkins & Globerson, 1991) and to adopt a scaffolding role for human cognition (Jong, 2005)

The role of a scaffolder is just one amidst many roles AI can assume in the coupling with humans (e.g. coach, assistant, companion) (Cui & Yasseri, 2024). As a scaffolding cognitive partner, we would expect an AI to be able to guide the thinking of a given Observer in relation to their Target System of Interest and to assist them in operating in their ZPD (Sætra, 2022), but not to think "for them". Eventually, under certain circumstances, where the coupling between the AI and the human is complex enough, there could be conditions for a co-augmentation of intelligence and for the emergence of capabilities and outcomes that cannot be simply reduced to the capacities or individual contributions of either agents (Melo, 2022).

Sætra (2022) highlights six characteristics of effective scaffolding, as proposed by Wood et al., 1976, namely: (i) motivation, (ii) direction maintenance, (iii) frustration control, (iv) simplification, (v) marking critical features, and (vi) demonstration. Holton and Clarke (2006) had previously expanded the notion of scaffolding, from Wood, Bruner and Ross (1976, cit in Holton & Clarke, 2006) and Vygotsky's ZPD (1978), with a conceptualisation framework that includes the following dimensions: (i) scaffolding agency (expert, reciprocal, or self-scaffolding); (ii) scaffolding domain (conceptual and heuristic); (iii) equating self-scaffolding with metacognition; (iv) zones of scaffolding which combine the previous criteria to compose a gradation of types of scaffolding situations (e.g. moving from conceptual to heuristic, from expert to self-scaffolding). Holton and Clarke (2006) review other proposals of sets of scaffolding questions for supporting metacognition (which they view as a form of self-scaffolding) that can be used across these zones. The idea that cognition can be scaffolded through questions, that would help the cognitive agent move beyond their current understanding, points to ways in which AI agents can be mobilised into scaffolding roles to promote CT. Forms of dialogical scaffolding that imply argumentation-based reasoning have also been proposed as a way to enhance the scope and quality of joint reasoning of humans and AI and of increasing value alignment (Mogdil, 2018). The use of scaffolding through questions is particularly well suited for use with AI based on Large Language Models (LLMs) and which allow for interactions in natural language.

In exploring the potential role of AI in scaffolding human learning, Sætra (2022) appeals to work on Intelligent Tutorial Systems by Brusilovskiy (1999, cit in., Sætra, 2022) which are organised in 4 modules: (i) a *teaching module* (with domain facts, rules and knowledge); (ii) a *learner model* (with learner skills, progress and general profile) and a (iii) *tutoring strategy* (theory of learning and tutoring), and an *interface*. The author proposes that a specialised adaptive

AI expert scaffolding Intelligent Tutorial System system can be organised similarly, with or without assistance of human experts.

1.3 Large Language Models and Prompt engineering

Generative LLMs have opened new possibilities for Human-AI interaction towards the assemblage of systems of augmented intelligence. LLMs, arising from the field of machine learning, are generative AI systems that are built upon underlying foundation models that are pre-trained to learn the relationships between tokens (typically fragments/roots of words) extracted from multiple extensive text corpora. The distinctive aspect of LLMs is the vast number of parameters (such as weights, biases, embedding vectors) that specify them: e.g. OpenAI's GPT 3.5 model is estimated to have around 20 billion parameters. LLMs can also have additional layers of training that fine-tune their output (text) in response to input (text aka prompts). This training can include evaluation of: completion of specific tasks, ability to follow instructions, and importantly, the degree to which responses stay within the bounds of a defined set of norms and values (aka alignment). The performance of LLMs is judged through the quality and relevance of their responses across various scenarios (for more information on LLMs see Naveed et al, 2023). The advent of ChatGPT (based on GPT 3.5) in November 2022 saw the crossing of critical thresholds of performance and accessibility, generating huge publicity, and initiating an explosion in the number of developers, applications, and lay users, massively accelerating a burgeoning boom in AI. The success of ChatGPT saw the advent of several popular LLMs available for free or subscription, and an increasing embedding of AI-assistance in multiple technology platforms.

LLMs are configured to generate outputs in response to a prompt. White and collaborators (2023) define a prompt as “set of instructions provided to an LLM that programs the LLM by customizing it and/or enhancing or refining its capabilities A prompt can influence subsequent interactions with—and output generated from—an LLM by providing specific rules and guidelines for an LLM conversation with a set of initial rules. In particular, a prompt sets the context for the conversation and tells the LLM what information is important and what the desired output form and content should be” (White et al., 2023, p.1). Prompt engineering is, hence, the way in which “LLMs are programmed” (White et al., 2023, p.1). There are four general elements of a prompt: (i) an *instruction*, (ii) a *context* (to steer better responses), (iii) *input data or question* and (iv) an *output indicator* (type or format) (Saravia, 2022). There are also a variety of approaches to prompting, aimed at optimising the interactions with the AI, usually emphasising iterative processes (Velásquez-Henao et al., 2023; Ray, 2023; Sarrion, 2023), and highlighting aspects such as detailed descriptions, context specification and step-by-step reasoning approaches (Ye et al., 2023; Ray, 2023).

Some patterns have been identified that may be more effective for particular LLMs and that can be adapted to different contexts (White et al., 2023). Aiming at specificity and accuracy can, however, lead to increased neutrality and less meaningful outputs. Therefore, some authors chose to adopt an alternative hermeneutic approach, with a focus on meaning (Henrickson & Meroño-Peñuela, 2023). Although sharing some similarities with programming, prompt engineering is more of an art or craft than traditional programming (Open AI, 2023; Google, 2024; Zamfirescu-Pereira et al., 2023). There are general rules of thumb to guide the formulation of prompts that can be applied across most LMMs, but each LLM has its own features, or ‘personalities’, requiring specific adjustments of the prompting process.

The level of creativity of the LLM's response to (human's) prompts can often be altered by changing the 'temperature' of the model which adjusts the output (Open AI, 2023). Higher levels of creativity produce less predictable (or potentially off-topic or tangential) responses. There is therefore a balance to be found between how 'free' the LLM is to be 'creative', versus how much the user wants the response to remain on-topic. High levels of 'creativity' increases the likelihood of 'hallucinations' (Open AI, 2023) the term used for when an LLM produces what is essentially made up nonsense, and how much of a problem that is depends on the task.

1.4 Exploring possibilities of interaction of a Complex Thinking Framework and Large Language Models for Scaffolding Complex Thinking

In this paper, we describe the process and outcome of a short exploratory study aiming at exploring the possibilities for the interaction between a complex thinking framework and generative AI based on Large Language Models (LLM), namely regarding the development of a tool for scaffolding Complex Thinking. In particular, this study aimed at (i) developing and conducting preliminary pilot evaluations of (suite of) protocols for AI (LLM) tools to scaffold CT of an individual or group in relation to a given TSoI (i.e. a real-world system, a problem, a concern), in order to develop more complex understandings of such systems that could guide more effective and positive actions and decisions; (ii) identify possibilities and limitations of the interaction of a CT framework and AI (LLM) tools. We describe the process and outcomes of the development and pilot evaluation of a suite of prompt protocols for scaffolding particular properties of Complex Thinking.

2. Method

2.1 Participants

In the different stages of development of the protocols (cf. below) there were two different groups of participants, both internal and external to the team, who were involved in pilot tests and evaluations of the tool (LLM + prompt protocols suite). Within the internal participants, two team members (*dev.int.user#1* and *dev.int.user#2*) were more deeply involved in the direct development of the prompt protocols as well as in conducting preliminary tests during the initial development stages. One was the author of the theoretical framework, and both had previously developed a qualitative method to evaluate complex thinking (Melo & Renault, 2023, 2024), therefore having experience in evaluating CT, within this framework, specifically the thinking underlying case conceptualisation of community-based family support practitioners. These two participants are both female with training in Psychology. Another member of the team, (*dev.inter.user#3*) collaborated in the development of earlier protocols but did not act as a test participant. Two other members of the team (*tech.int#1* and *tech.int#2*) assisted with some of the internal tests and contributed to addressing technical issues related to the development of the protocols but did not participate in the development tests of the protocols as users. At a later phase, two other team members who had not been directly involved in the development of the protocols acted as users in two pilot case study tests (case studies 1 and 2) of more robust versions of the protocols. These participants, (*int.user#1* and *int.user#2*), male and female, respectively, are both PhD level researchers, the latter being a social psychologist conducting research on housing issues and inequalities and the former (*int.user#2*) a sociologist conducting research on the execution of

security measures by mentally disordered offenders (*int.user#1*). They used their research domains as TSoI in their tests.

We conducted two more case studies pilot tests with external participants. This group was divided into two subsets. Case studies 3 and 4, included two academics, with research problems, one focused on the domain of Futures research (*ext.user#1*) and the other on applied research on social-ecological systems (*ext.user#2*). Both of these users had Masters-level education. While *ext.user#1* was experienced using AI tools *ext.user#2* had had no previous experience. Case studies 5 and 6 included a second subset of external participants, corresponding to two teams of community-based family support practitioners (*ext.user#3* and *ext.user#4*). These teams had very applied focuses. Their work implies conducting assessments and interventions with families with at-risk and endangered children and youth which is supported by their case conceptualisation. The exploration of the AI tool was done in pairs, by two team members. Both teams had received training in CT before and were familiar with the process of case conceptualisation. All participants provided written informed consent regarding the conditions for their participation and data collection.

2.2 Ethics statement

This study obtained ethical approval (REF 90/24) from the Ethics Committee of the Centre for Social Studies of the University of Coimbra.

2.3 LLMs as a platform for the scaffolding tool

For our purposes, we explored using LLMs as a platform for developing the scaffolding tool. Given the time constraints of the project and the resources available, we used a text prompting approach through the web interfaces, and did not explore the use of APIs. In this project we wanted to constrain the behaviour of the LLMs (beyond technical parameters such as setting the temperature or selecting pre-defined personas suggesting different levels of creativity) by giving the LLMs protocols that ‘encode’ aspects of a CT framework. These protocols shape the response of the LLMs to the prompts of the human in a way that allows them both (human/AI) to work collaboratively on the thinking process.

Through the course of the development of the protocols, we experimented with the use of different LLM platforms (at the level of the pro/paid subscription): ChatGPT 4/4o (OpenAI); Claude Sonnet 3.5 (Anthropic) and Sonar (Perplexity). We also experimented with other platforms (e.g. Google Gemini, a local instance of Ollama) but to a lesser extent. We initiated our tests with Chat GTP 4o. We then made parallel tests comparing Chat GPT with Perplexity, using its default model and later on introduced Claude Sonnet 3.5 in comparison with Chat GPT 4o. The final protocols were fine-tuned for Claude as further described below.

2.4 Development of the protocols

The development of the prototypes of protocols for scaffolding CT with LLMs proceeded through an iterative process comprising a set of key phases, described below. The process was iterative both within and between phases. We implemented and conducted preliminary checks and tests on the performance of the protocols during the development stages and several rounds of refinements after the pilot tests with internal and external users.

2.4.1 Development phase 1: Requirements and aims of the scaffolding process

In this stage, we analysed the requirements set up by the theoretical framework on CT and clarified the aim of the scaffolding process.

2.4.4.1 Requirements and challenges of the implementation of a Complex Thinking Framework. The theoretical framework guiding this study (Melo, 2020) encompasses a particular set of assumptions about the nature of cognition as an embodied, enactive, embedded and extended process (Newen, Bruin & Gallagher, 2018) and its underlying (predominantly constructivist) ontology and epistemology as an activity performed by a particular observer in relation to its environment and a particular context. The framework also proposes a very particular definition of CT. The design of any tool or strategy to scaffold CT needed to be congruent with the theoretical assumptions and foundations of the framework. The theoretical framework then sets up specific requirements which pose particular challenges, in particular for the development of an AI-based tool. Table 1 lists some of the core requirements derived from the framework that guided the decisions and problem-solving efforts of the team, along with the challenges identified for both humans and the AI, and how we addressed the challenges.

Table 1. Requirements of the Complex Thinking framework for the scaffolding process

Requirements	Challenges to humans	Challenges related to AI (LLM) tools	How challenge was addressed
Complex Thinking requires the performance of various types of thinking movements of different degrees of difficulty	Certain movements are difficult to perform to humans (e.g. restrictions of memory; multidimensionality of information); Limitations of the repertoires of practices for thinking movements.	Certain movements are more difficult to perform by an AI (e.g. intentionality, pragmatic, aesthetic, ethical values) (cf. alignment problem); The social and cultural sensitivity required for supporting thinking movements is missing.	AI is prompted to support thinking movements that are possible to scaffold, and to manage the storage and organisation of information. AI is prompted to prompt the user to make external ethical, aesthetic, social and cultural checks.
The organisation of Complex Thinking is relational and requires the interaction between different thinking movements and the information that results from them	Difficulty of keeping awareness of the variety of thinking movements, choosing the movements in relation to each other; Relating and integrating and composing (Choreographing)	Difficulty attuning to intentionality, purpose, restricted modes of coupling with the observer (based mostly on verbal language) “Lack of intuition” (e.g. cue in; be guided the information); Need a “meta-tool” capable of orchestrating the coordination of different	The AI guides the user in performing thinking movements within a certain property. Other thinking movements are embedded in the scaffolding of that target property. No meta-tool is currently developed to coordinate modules.

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		scaffolding modules for different properties	
Information emergent from relations and relational movements requires exploration	Limited memory and mapping capacities for visualising and navigating the relational structure of information/	Limited memory and mapping capacities for visualising and navigating the relational structure of information.	AI invites users to capture information and relations through metaphors and offers visualisation of such metaphors. AI provides summaries and visual overall maps of the information. Relational mapping still limited
The (configurations of) thinking movements (processes) need to be dynamically traced along contents	Variations and limitations of meta-cognitive capacities and difficulty tracking process of thinking along contents	Needs to be capable of mapping various thinking movements and their coordination by moment and the nuances of their complexity along the unfolding of contents. Needs specific “training” and a reference database	Not currently addressed
Ongoing reflexivity (in self and hetero scaffolding);	Difficult of keeping awareness of its “blindspots”, personal constraints and habits of thinking and how their experiences shape the ongoing thinking;	Absence of “true” reflexivity (lacks self-awareness)	AI can prompt and induce reflexivity by pointing to particular types of processes and invite the user to conduct activities that may increase reflexivity, namely involving other reflexive agents.
The thinking is embodied and enactive. It is necessary to allow for a (recursive, embodied, active) manipulation, mapping, updating and retrieval of complex information (e.g. relational, multi-level, multi-temporal scales	Limited memory and capacity to hold complex information	Memory and limitations with interface (in terms of allowing physical manipulation of information)	AI prompts the user to perform active embodied activities, outside of the tool to physically and metaphorically manipulate and explore the information. Use Artifacts function on Claude to generate a variety of types of outputs, namely visual, that the user can interact with and

			manipulate and keep present alongside the dialogue).
The facilitation of emergence (new hypothesis, ideas) requires experiments with multiple alternative independent thinking trajectories as much as exploring path-dependent ways. Path-dependence and independence both need to be explored	Non-linearity and randomness of thinking movements are difficult to manage (path-independent)	AI needs to forget a pathway to open new ones, but also to remember to guide the user in exploring its contingencies and to find patterns	Not currently addressed
‘Fitness’ (e.g. pragmatic, ethical value and integrity and accuracy) of the thinking and information and ‘good enough’ complexity	Limited perspectives; preconceptions, prejudices, stereotypes.	The problem of association; “hallucination”, speculative, prejudices, stereotypes; Absence of pragmatic, aesthetic, ethical values; Inability of directly coupling the target system in terms of values.	Double reflexive effort for humans: they keep themselves and the AI in check. AI is prompted to have the human perform such checks with external sources.
The process of scaffolding needs to generate coherence and (sufficient) difference in the coupling between entities or with the TSoI to scaffold nature/level of complexity of the thinking	The complexity of the human will affect their coupling with d the coupling with the framework and their metacognitive capacities to guide an ongoing nuanced evaluation that can guides the coupling with another Human or TSoI	The complexity of the AI and the coupling with the framework for an ongoing performance evaluation that guides the coupling with another Human or TSoI are a challenge. Difficulties of “attuning” (multiple types of coupling) to the observer and their domain and the social-cultural specificity of the context where the thinking movements are performed and the variety of ways they can be performed; Asymmetrical coupling AI-human	Not directly addressed. Recommendations for using the protocols along with the presence of a Human scaffolder familiar with and with expertise in the framework and sufficient complexity to couple both with the human user and the AI.

2.4.4.2 Aims of the scaffolding process. Our goal was to develop a set of protocols for AI (LLM) tools to support individuals (or groups) in performing CT in relation to a given TSoI (a real-world system, a problem, a concern) in order to develop more complex understandings of

such systems that could guide more effective and positive actions and decisions. Our focus was not to have an AI tool providing answers or solutions to a problem but to engage with and guide, within the principles of the CT framework, a user in their own process of thinking so as to increase its complexity. The target complexity of the thinking is, hence, located in the coupling relation between the individual and their TSoI although we also aimed for the process of interaction with the AI to be sufficiently complex so as to lead to some emergent insights and ideas. Our aim for the scaffolding tool was to stay relatively coupled, to some extent, to the user's thinking, working from their existing level of complexity and then to provide support for the user to perform more complex thinking movements. The tool should provide scaffolding such that it introduces a degree of novelty but not excessively so. Any suggestions should be to support the user in moving towards thinking that is relatively more complex, but not to "think for" the user. This created a strong requirement for a robust evaluation framework that would set up the key constraints for the LLM tool to operate and that would allow it to make proposals based on the complexity of the user's response.

2.4.4.3 Critical guiding criteria in developing the prompt protocols. Given the theoretical constraints of the chosen framework, a challenge in developing the scaffolding protocols was finding a balance between different aspects of the LLMs responses, which we conceptualised as: Boundaries, Attunement and Variation (see Figure 1). We intentionally looked at these criteria and worked to balance them in relation to each other: Boundaries relates to the requirement to stay within prescribed (or desired) *bounds*: e.g. confining the responses to within the CT framework itself and taking its evaluation framework as a reference, which results from *keeping within the scope and context* of the phases, steps and modes of the protocols. Another distinctive requirement was to maintain the *focus of attention* on the *processes* of the user(s) thinking rather than on the content. An additional ethical consideration was to instruct the tool to refrain from making any decisions (for the user) and offering any suggestions for interventions or decisions in relation to the TSoI; Attunement relates to the requirement for *adapting* to the user(s) context. Examples are: adapting both the selection and modification of generic scaffolding questions to be appropriate to the user(s) particular context; adaption of the protocol e.g. choice of moves within/between modes, according to the responses of the user(s). Another aspect is *engaging* with the user(s). Examples include: adopting a dialogical style that adapts to the user(s) own way of expressing themselves; stimulating curiosity and motivation for engagement; Variation relates to the requirement that the tool adds or creates information as "differences that make a difference" (Bateson, 1979, p. 99). This can take many forms, such as adding *organisation* or *nuance* to existing information. An important aspect for the CT framework was for the tool to *suggest embodied activities* that go beyond the more propositional type of knowledge(s) elicited by the principally text-based mode of interaction. A characteristic of these additions is their *novelty* to the user(s) and the experience of *surprise*. A combination of attunement and variation was critical for the tool to *explore and flesh out metaphor(s)* offered by the user(s), offering nuanced perspectives while staying within the scope of the meaning constructed by the user.

Figure 1. Considerations in developing the prompts to achieve the desired balance in the protocols.

2.4.2 Development phase 2: Operationalising the theoretical framework

The adopted framework for CT proposes 9 dimensions and 24 properties of the thinking. It also postulates that the (non-linear) interaction between the thinking movements associated with the different properties is critical for the complexity of the thinking as an outcome and for creative and abductive emergence. Given the short term nature of this exploratory project and the complexity of the framework, we targeted only a small subset of properties. We chose to focus on the dimension of *Structural Complexity of the Thinking* and the corresponding properties of *Structural Variety and Dimensionality* and of *Relationality*, given their centrality to generating (sufficiently complex) *contents* of the thinking upon which other thinking movements are performed. A full implementation of a scaffolding system for CT would require the design of specific protocol modules for the scaffolding of each of the properties as well as meta-modules to guide the orchestration and integration of movements associated with the non-linear and recursive interaction between the different properties. Such an effort was not feasible within the scope of the project; our initial aim was to establish the feasibility of using LLMs to scaffold CT. Nevertheless, since (relatively) more complex thinking is predicated on the interaction between a variety of different CT thinking movements, it was necessary to ensure some degree of interaction or modulation of one property by another. Therefore, for each module we implemented, alongside questions and activities focusing on the target CT property, we created lists of what we call *embedding modulating questions* to be used in combination with questions or activities focused on scaffolding the target property. These questions, although still focused on the target property,

do so in relation to other dimensions such as the *Complexity of the Observer*, and the properties of *Multipositioning*, *Reflexivity* and *Intentionalities*.

2.4.3 Development Phase 3. Development of an evaluation framework

As mentioned above, there was a strong requirement for setting boundary constraints. A robust evaluation framework should establish the criteria to evaluate the current level of complexity of the expressed thinking of the user(s). This stage of work built upon experience of operationalising the CT framework for the development of a visual mapping method for CT, Complexigraphy (Melo & Renault, 2023, 2024). The aim was to identify the core distinctive features of the performance of each property, the definition of different levels of complexity, and evaluation indicators. For example, we developed a detailed evaluation of the sub-property of *multidimensionality and variety of contents of the thinking*, which considers a high number of content descriptive dimensions that, theoretically, we determined were necessary for a minimally complex description of a TSoI: (i) the *internal organisation of the system*, (ii) its *environment*, (iii) the *observer* and (iv) the *coupling between these dimensions*. Each of these dimensions had their own sub-dimensions. The evaluation required attending to a variety of sub-properties and indicators simultaneously and in relation to each other.

This framework, when implemented, would allow the tool to adapt its responses in relation to the current level of complexity of the user(s) thinking. Several versions of this evaluation framework were created, and were refined, alongside the development and calibration of the evaluation protocol to be used by the LLM.

2.4.4 Development Phase 4. Development and calibration of the evaluation protocol

Several iterations were required in the development cycle of the prompt protocol for the evaluation of the complexity of the thinking for the dimension of *Structural Complexity*. We started with the evaluation of the property *Structural Variety and Dimensionality* and then moved onto the property of *Relationality*.

2.4.4.1 Protocol development. We started to implement the evaluation framework by trying to provide the LLM with a detailed description of the properties, levels and indicators of complexity within the CT framework that could be used to perform an evaluation of a given text or case (initially we used some selected short case studies/reports across domains, though see subsection on Calibration below). At that time, supplying data to the LLMs via spreadsheet, resulted in many errors that were never satisfactorily resolved. An alternative approach using documents with hyperlinks for the definition of each property and indicators also failed. Ultimately, we adopted a detailed step-by-step narrative approach to deliver the property descriptions and the evaluation protocol. It was critical to have the tool systematically track and accurately consider all dimensions and sub-dimensions since the evaluation of all other properties of CT are built and evaluated “on top” of this basic content structure. When provided with the protocol, the tool appeared to try to synthesise and provide only an overall evaluation of properties, and to ignore lower-level sub-properties or indicators, or to focus too much on some details, while ignoring others. Worse, it might also rely on its own interpretation of the properties. It was these kinds of challenges that shaped the development of our prompting strategies, including the structuring of the protocol documents and disambiguation of references to critical text via unique identifiers (summarised in the Technical Aspects section below). At later stages of the development of the protocols, we started to test recursive references to the evaluation criteria

and to critical pieces of information, to ensure they were “carried over” between stages of the evaluations within a property, and between properties, and kept in consideration throughout the dialogue. This kind of recursive loop allowed us to stabilise the protocols and to ensure that the responses of the tool were grounded in the CT framework and attuned to the user(s) context.

2.4.4.2 Calibration of the evaluation protocols. To support calibration of the evaluation protocols we used the LLM to develop a narrative about a fictitious scenario where an Observer is reporting the problems and concerns of a given community via a descriptive narrative that intends to convey a complex understanding of the situation. We initiated the development of this scenario on ChatGPT 4o. The imaginary community was called *Rivertown* by the tool. We adopted a stepwise process whereby we instructed the model to add details to an initial narrative related to each of the sub-properties and indicators. We started with the development of a *high* complexity narrative and then developed relatively *moderate* and *low* complexity narratives from it. We conducted several tests of the evaluation protocol using the three *Rivertown* scenarios. We compared different LLMs and experimented with different approaches for the prompts.

2.4.5 Development Phase 5. Organisation of the scaffolding modules and prototyping of scaffolding prompt protocols

To attend to the requirements of the framework, the protocols needed to include different modes of scaffolding. The principal modes for the tool are the *dialogical scaffolding* mode and the *evaluation* mode.

2.4.5.1 Dialogical scaffolding mode. We prepared a protocol of prompts for the AI to support the user by presenting questions that would guide the thinking while taking into account the indicators and levels of complexity for the property at stake and adjusting the questions to an evaluation of that complexity. Building from the evaluation framework and the definition of the targeted properties we assembled a database of scaffolding questions to guide the LLM in supporting the user in developing and increasing the complexity of their thinking. These questions were organised into different categories to be used in different moments of the scaffolding process. Particular categories of questions were created to ensure that the unfolding of thinking is purposeful and attuned to the user’s intentions but also to modulate the thinking with critical complex thinking movements such as those associated with the *Complexity of the Observer*, namely *Multi-Positioning*, *Reflexivity* and *Intentionalities*. This mode builds upon the capabilities of the models for natural language.

2.4.5.2 Evaluation mode. In this mode, the tool offered the user an explicit and structured evaluation with feedback about the complexity of their expressed thinking. However, the evaluation mode was also invoked by the tool to conduct implicit evaluations to support choosing and adapting the scaffolding questions. The refinement of the protocol through the evaluation mode was critical to adapting the protocol to the context and in ensuring satisfactory results (although varying with different models, as reported in the Results section).

2.4.5.3. Other modes. We conducted tests as we were developing the protocol allowing for progressive refinements and fine-tuning. As the dialogical scaffolding and evaluation modes were performing minimally well, we expanded the prompting to cover other modes of scaffolding and to address the framework requirements, integrating them in the protocols (see Results below, Table 2 and Figure 2).

2.4.6 Development Phase 6. Prototyping pilot testing with internal user

Once we achieved what we considered to be a minimally robust protocol we conducted more systematic pilot tests of the protocols. Case studies 1 and 2 included two internal users (int.user#1 and int.user#2) who tested the protocols with different intentionalities and target problems, under supervision. This allowed us to identify additional limitations of the current approach and to introduce additional nuances in the modes of the protocols. There were two independent sessions conducted with each user. Each session lasted approximately 90 min. For subsequent analysis, these sessions were audio and video recorded and the logs of the chat were extracted from the LLM tool.

2.4.7 Development Phase 7. Prototyping pilot testing with external user pilot tests

Additional pilot tests (case studies 3 to 6) were conducted with external users in the presence of the team (one session for case studies 3 and 4 and two sessions for case studies 5 and 6). During the sessions the team provided support, sometimes intentionally nudging the user to try particular steps or approaches to test the robustness of the protocols. The team also recorded the user's most salient reactions and reports of their experience. Each session lasted approximately between 120 and 180 minutes. For subsequent analysis, these sessions were audio and video recorded and the logs of the chat were extracted from the LLM tool. At the end of each session there was a short interview to explore the participant's experience. Additionally, the participating teams completed a post-session reflection commenting on their session log.

2.4.8 Development Phase 8. Final refinement of the protocols

Based on the previous phase, opportunities for further improvements of the protocols were also identified, leading to the fine tuning of the protocols and the introduction of minor adjustments.

2.5 Technical Aspects of the Tool Development Process

2.5.1 Features of the adopted prompting strategy

We highlight the following aspects of our approach to developing the prompts that make up the evaluation and scaffolding protocols:

- 1) Use of documents with hierarchical structure, containing: (i) an *introduction* and (ii) definition of the *role* of the AI, followed by (iii) general *guidance*, which sets up the contexts, and details the different *modes* of scaffolding, corresponding artifacts and what is expected as an outcome and by the AI, (iv) instructions hierarchically organised into *phases* and *steps*, each calling upon different modes of scaffolding;
- 2) Adopting of an algorithmic approach with procedures and branching (e.g. "If-Then" conditional branching);
- 3) Use of identifiers (or tags) to ensure disambiguation of references within and between modules to text describing the context, phases and dimensions of the thinking. Identifiers were denoted by text between square brackets e.g. [DSCAFF MODE] (NB. any convention would likely suffice e.g. hash tags, or HTML-like angle brackets etc.);
- 4) Adopting a hierarchical naming scheme for identifiers that reflects the structure i.e. dimensions and properties of the Complex Thinking framework e.g. [SC.SVD.MD.O.MOD.OC.MP.FMODQ1]. This was applied to all the questions allowing us to evaluate more easily how they were being used by the tools;

- 5) The interaction (between the tool and the user) is framed by a “General First Instruction” document, which introduces the CT framework and defines Complex Thinking and the organisation of the framework into dimensions and properties;
- 6) Non-linearity: the tool guides thinking iterations following the different steps sequentially, but also is instructed to give the user choices on how to proceed and which modes of scaffolding to engage with; depending on the responses some steps may be skipped;
- 7) Recursion: some choices may result in a re-entry into previous steps to deepen the scaffolding, forming recursive loops. This aligns with the importance of reflexivity in the CT framework;
- 8) Provision of guidance ([GUIDANCE]) to establish context for the LLM to try to minimise alternative “interpretations” or operating outside of the CT framework; Each phase has a general description of what is to be achieved
- 9) Use of precise instructions within the prompts to constrain responses and to try to define boundary conditions for the LLM to “stay within the framework”
- 10) Explicit reference through identifiers to particular documents/images that are generated/refined through the process (e.g. Claude’s Artifacts).

These elements work together to create a structured system of internal references (e.g. to guidance instructions or documents such as those detailing the evaluation framework and its dimensions, properties sub-properties and indicators, along a detailed description of modes of scaffolding and the role of AI) to ensure (or at least promote) a “tight(er)” and disambiguated protocol such that the AI’s suggestions and guidance were properly framed by the theoretical model, its assumptions and requirements. At the time of writing, each protocol document spanned from 3 to 16 pages. A list of the protocols developed can be found in Appendix A.

2.5.2 Technical challenges.

In developing the protocols, we encountered some challenges with the LLM platforms under evaluation. Perhaps most significant were issues related to the LLM context windows (often described as token counts or length), which is the amount of information related to the current chat that the LLM can keep in ‘memory’ and that shapes its responses. These limits differ across platforms and vary across different versions, generally becoming larger with later versions. We needed to pre-load protocol documents into the LLM, and then required the LLM to retain this information and use it during the subsequent dialogue. This step necessarily uses up some of the available ‘memory’ of the LLM. As a result, we did experience issues that appeared to relate to a loss of information or context. Also, we often hit platform usage limits, which could mean the need to stop the dialogue (or pause for some timeout period). With Claude, hitting session limits could become limiting, however session lengths before hitting system limits seemed to be inconsistent. We speculated that other factors were in play (system demand management, wider system status issues). Where possible, we took steps to mitigate token usage, some of which used platform specific features. We found that the platforms would not always behave consistently week-to-week, or sometimes day-to-day, as model features and refinements would seem to be trialled by the platform provider on an experimental basis, even within ostensibly the same LLM version. Given the very fast development cycle of the LLM platforms, we had to accept this as part of the terrain (and acknowledge that some of these issues might now be anachronistic, while anticipating that new challenges might arise).

2.6 Data analysis

Two members of the team (developer.inter.user#1 and 2) analysed all the transcriptions and log records of the chats. To try to identify core ideas and themes and regarding the evaluation and experience of the users, they first conducted an overall holistic coding followed by a descriptive open coding of selected passages (Saldaña, 2016).

3. Results

3.1 Choice of the LLM

Although not intended as a comprehensive assessment of their capabilities, we offer the following reflection of our experiences and the rationale for our choice of platform. ChatGPT appeared eager/impetuous, and tended to problematise prompts, readily offering up “solutions”, sometimes in a rather “lazy” manner, neglecting detail and “averaging” the information. ChatGPT would also lose track of the protocol fairly quickly, “running after” some theme that emerged, and the structure of the thinking process would collapse. Sonar was more structured but appeared rather rigid, and perhaps a little boring. However, it would adhere to the protocol quite closely, but without offering much creativity or insight. Claude had the best balance between keeping close enough to the protocols that it could facilitate the thinking process, whilst also having a degree of creativity in its responses that it could engage with the human user in a more natural way and remain coupled with their thinking, guided by the evaluation framework. For example, incorporating aspects of the prompts into its responses (e.g. if the input style was more narrative, it would tend to echo that in responses) which led to a more engaging interaction. The team - as a whole - found Claude to be an engaging, respectful and “insightful” dialogical partner. With the introduction of Artifacts (persistent, editable, versionable documents), Claude met some of our technical requirements in a natural way: it became the primary platform for the development of the scaffolding tool (LLM + protocol suite).

After identifying Claude as the model with the best fit for our intentions and best performance, the protocols continued to be developed, refined and fine-tuned for this model in particular. The results described below are from the tool using the Claude 3.5 Sonnet model only.

3.2 Organisation of modules for particular properties of CT and scaffolding modes

We organised different prompt protocols for scaffolding the dimension of *Structural Complexity*, namely the properties of *Structural Variety and Dimensionality* (SVD) and *Relationality* (R). While the sub-properties of SVD were all covered in the same protocol. For the property of *Relationality*, we created two different protocols for the sub-properties of *Relations as Entities* and *Relational Movements*, as the processes of their scaffolding appealed to a different logic.

Each module contains and combines different modes of scaffolding. Each of these modes and their combination in a module, allowed us to make approximations to the requirements and challenges posed by the theoretical framework for the scaffolding process. Table 2 summarises the 9 modes which are integrated in a module, their corresponding artifacts and a brief description of their key characteristics and core function. It also includes dimensions to be further developed or improved in the future. Figure 2 shows how the modes are coordinated and related, within a module.

Table 2. Summary of the modes integrating a prototype scaffolding module

Number and Identifier	Name	Corresponding artifact	Key characteristics and core function	Potential improvements
MODE 1 [EVAL MODE]	Evaluation Mode	[EVAL REPORT] Generates a report identifying and justifying the level of complexity for each property and sub-property and an overall evaluation	The evaluation offers feedback to the user on their thinking, supporting the AI in offering suggestions to improve this complexity and to guide the scaffolding (e.g. choosing and /or adapting most appropriate questions)	Not identified
MODE 2 [DSCAFF MODE]	Dialogical Scaffolding Mode	Not applicable	This is the default mode of interaction which is based on posing questions to the user and adjusting them to the level of complexity of their response (according to the criteria provided for the [EVAL MODE].	Allowing for the user to have a visual mapping of the point where they are in the scaffolding protocol and the freedom to move to particular points of the protocol. Allowing an experienced user to avoid the procedural questions and first foundational questions and choose the types of scaffolding question. Enrich the database of questions
MODE 3 [METAPHOR MODE]	Metaphorising Mode	[METAPHOR MAP] The AI tool generates visual, audio, or video artifact that captures the metaphors created by the user.	Supports the user with building a more embodied experience and holistic connection with the information. Supports the syntheses of complex, nuanced and multidimensional information. Increases	Explore the potential of working with different categories of metaphors. Prepare dialogical scaffolding questions around

			reflexivity and facilitates the direct manipulation of the information. Claude has offered unprompted an exploration of the metaphor making explicit key aspects of the metaphor in relation to a complex description and conceptualisation of the TSoI.	the exploration of the metaphor
MODE 4 [SYNTH MODE_ OPTION 1] AND [SYNTH MODE_ OPTION 2]	Synthesising Mode	[SYNTH MODE_OPTION 1] generates a TSoI_TABLE, a table organising the information about the TSoI according to the criteria of the theoretical framework for the contents that are necessary for a minimally complex description of the TSoI. [SYNTH MODE_OPTION 2] generates a [SYNTH MAP] a visual representation or mnemonics that helps the user grasp, capture and remember the essence of the information generated to that point in the dialogue about the TSoI.	Helps the user capture, organise and integrate the information creating visual and memory aids. Support the management of complex information and aids the user in performing recursive visits and checks on the information generated.	The layouts of the table need to be made more attractive. The SYNTH map can also have template layouts and can perhaps be further separated into a Map and Mnemonics, offering the user the option.
MODE 5 [MAP MODE]	Mapping Mode	[TSoI_MAP] organises the information about the TSoI by the	Contributes to increased reflexivity and awareness about the nature of the	The mapping of relations needs to be improved and more detailed and

		dimensions the framework considers necessary for a minimally complex description of the TSoI.	contents of the thinking, the ones more and less developed and where absences are more critical. Allows the user to be more active in determining the information they wish to deepen to increase complexity	nuanced. If very generic then less useful. This map should then be updated to support the visualisation and outcomes off relational movements.
MODE 6 [NARRATIVE MODE]	Narrative Mode	[TSoI_Narrative] Creates a narrative about the TSoI, capturing the thinking developed so far.	This mode helps the user capture the thinking developed so far in a narrative mode thereby creating conditions for recursion and revisitation of areas already covered for further improvements and to increase reflexivity by helping the user become more aware of the possibilities and limitations of the thinking. The narrative supports the sharing and coordination of the thinking with external others.	Different kinds of narrative can be created that may afford different possibilities. Options can be given to the user, e.g. for literary style narratives vs., journalistics, reporte type.
MODE 7 [NOTES MODE]	Notes Mode	[OBS NOTES] Captures the emergent ideas or insights the user has during the scaffolding process.	This mode aims at supporting the user in the organisation of their thinking and helps increase reflexivity about its emergent outcomes. It supports the capture, management, and retrieval of information. It facilitates integration of the moment by moment outcomes of the thinking, and the emergent information, into the overall process.	The emergent ideas should be mapped onto the relational maps like the TSoI_MAP and updated in them.

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<p>MODE 8 [ACTIVE SCAFF TSoI MODE]</p>	<p>Active Scaffolding <i>TSoI</i> Mode</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>This mode aims to support a direct engagement with the user with their TSoI (and their environments) in order to generate meaningful information that increases the complexity of their thinking (coupling). It also allows for the creation and exploration of more embodied information generated in an active direct engagement with the TSoI. The tool provides suggestions of activities that can be carried as a function of the dimensions that require improvement.</p>	<p>A richer database of activities that support the enactment of a wide array of property and sub-properties of CT can be built drawing from different domains.</p>
<p>MODE 9 [ACTIVE SCAFF SELF MODE]</p>	<p>Active Scaffolding <i>Self</i> Mode</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>This mode aims to support a self-referential exploration of the thinking, proposing active and embodied activities that allow the user to consider and explore their role as an observer in the construction of the TSoI and the exploration of the nature of their own thinking. It promotes reflexivity and an embodied and situated approach to the thinking about the TSoI.</p>	<p>A richer database of activities that support the enactment of a wide array of property and sub-properties of CT can be built drawing from different domains.</p>

Figure 2. Organisation of each module in 9 modes of scaffolding and their relations

The evaluation mode ([EVAL MODE]) is critical as it is connected with all others and guides the tool in adjusting the options presented to the user. This mode supports and shapes the central dialogical scaffolding mode ([DSCAFF MODE]) around which the core dialogue is organised. The dialogical model focuses mostly on the target property of the module but also it includes the exploration of a relation between that property and other critical modulating properties (e.g. those related to the *Complexity of the Observer*), embedding them in modulating questions. The *dialogical scaffolding mode* includes different categories of questions, fulfilling different purposes, namely: (i) *procedural questions*: provide support to the user regarding the scaffolding process, e.g. offering basic instructions or a tutorial on basic terms used; (ii) *foundational questions*: supports the thinking in generating information for a minimally complex description of their TSol; (iii) *foundational modulating questions*: questions that modulate the description of the TSol modulated by other properties, namely regarding the *Complexity of the Observer*; (iv) *scaffolding questions*- contribute to deepen the complexity of the thinking of the observer in terms of the target property; (v) *scaffolding modulating questions*: which deepened the modulation of the target property and of the scaffolding questions with other critical properties. The protocol included a sequence of steps where these different questions were recruited and some recursive loops whereby some categories of questions were revisited, for deepening purposes, after a first iteration. The complex and multi-layered information that is generated through this process can be captured and synthesised in a variety of artifacts which allow the user to see, retain and manipulate the information, namely in a more embodied way. Modes 3 ([METAPHOR MODE]), 4 ([SYNTH MODE]), 5 ([MAP MODE]) to 6 ([NARRATIVE MODE]) support these processes, through visual, diagrammatic, sound, audio, movement of narrative means, depending on the specific mode and corresponding artifact. The resulting maps, syntheses and narratives can be subject to new evaluations to provide clearer feedback to the users and then further guide the continuation of the scaffolding process.

The dialogical scaffolding is interspersed with an *active scaffolding mode*, either focused on *the TSoI or the Self*. Information resulting from these activities can then be added to updated artifacts from modes 3 to 6 but also evaluated to the extent that they contribute to the complexity of the thinking. The *notes mode* ([NOTES MODE]) gathers ideas that result from the whole process and generates information that can be further explored through different modes. Some of the relations and transitions between these modes are covered by the protocol but they can also be called on demand by the user, who is given, at the onset of the interaction, an overview of the different modes.

Users can drive the interaction in particular directions that would make the tool lose the context of the protocol or the aim of promoting CT under the guidance of our framework. Therefore, we added an instruction in the following prompt: “ If the observer starts making other questions and requests that are unrelated or that move the dialogue away from the scaffolding protocol, and the different modes of scaffolding that are previewed, answer always in ways that would support the [OBS] “Observer” in increasing the complexity of their thinking as described in the documents CT_CODING_STRUCTURAL VARIETY_EVALUATION MODE_NARRATIVE INSTRUCTIONS, particularly considering the dimensions and sub-dimensions for a minimally complex description of the TSoI. Immediately after resume the scaffolding to the last step that was performed according to instructions.”

Although the tool would make some natural adjustments in relation to the user(s) style of interaction, the final evaluation tests pointed to the relevance of making additional refinements to the *narrative mode* to allow the user to choose the style of the narrative to be created (e.g. choosing between a more literary or more journalistic/succinct style) since they would stimulate different types of thinking but also be used for different purposes. For example, the family support team of practitioners considered the narratives to be very useful. While the literary style narratives offered them interesting ways to share their hypothesis with the families they worked in an effective and “beautiful” or inspiring way, the more journalistic narrative helped them structure information in ways that were useful in preparing reports (e.g. assessment case reports to send to courts or child protection systems).

3.3 Prototype pilot testing: lessons learned, strengths, limitations and suggestions for improvement

Each case study had a particular context and focus, with the exception of 5 and 6, which had similar foci. In Appendix B we describe the context and purpose, and highlight the most distinctively positive and negative features of each case study. In Appendix C we present selected excerpts of the chats, illustrating particular modes of scaffolding and some of the most salient features of the interaction of the user with the tool. Overall, the case studies contributed to further refinements and adjustments of the protocols. The analysis of all the data (logs with memos regarding the tests, videos, transcripts and session logs) allowed us to identify some patterns regarding the more salient features of the tool (LLM + protocols) and their effects. Table 3 summarises these patterns in terms of strengths and limitations of the tool (Claude Sonnet 3.5 + protocols) and their effects. We mark our perception of their power with: (+++) for the most salient strengths, (++) to moderate or less salient and (+) to a less salient strength; (---) for the most salient limitations, (--) for moderate limitations or less stable ones and (-) for minor limitations.

Table 3. Strengths and limitations of the tool (Claude Sonnet 3.5 + protocol suite)

Strengths		Limitations	
Coupling User-Tool and General Performance			
“Natural”, fluid engagement	+++	“Verbose” interaction	-
Good coupling: Tool acts as reflexive partner staying close to the user thinking and supporting but not thinking for them, while introducing some difference and variation	+++	Technical information [identifiers] is not omitted	-
Good adaptation: adapting questions and activities to context	+++	Coupling can be lost in the transition to other protocols when procedural questions and foundational questions are not revisited to create a stronger connection with the TSoI	--
Transition between protocols facilitated by uploading previous artifacts	++	Transition between protocols is poor (Properties)	
Returns to protocol after some deviation from it (e.g. addressing a user’s question) making the connection with the closest scaffolding questions	++	May not return to protocol promptly or when “pushed” significantly out of it	-
Element of surprise and stimulation of curiosity that supports engagement	+++	Sometimes presents too much information having an “overwhelming” effect	++
Mostly consistent performance with chose model	++	Some erratic, “off order” but “in protocol” mode interactions	-
		Model-specific performance of the protocol	---
Dialogical Scaffolding: Questions			
Generative, productive, interesting questions	+++	Sometimes “massive” and difficult to answer (immediately)	--
Adaptation and choice of questions to user’s context and preferences	+++	Calls upon a concrete context of application or TSOI	-
Generates engagement, sustains attention	++		
Relationality associated with more new perspectives and insights and creative	++		

effect			
Scaffolding through metaphors: Metaphorical mode			
Metaphors support the coupling tool/user bringing the dialogue closer to the references of the user	+++	Sometimes offers metaphors spontaneously	-
Metaphors situate the thinking and support the connection with rich embodied information ; Brings the user closer to their own thinking and capable of interacting with it	+++		
Tool “unpacks”, explores the metaphor in a ways that add and highlight other or implicit perspectives and nuances	+++		
Metaphor supports a richer coupling of the tool/-user and user with their TSoI	+++		
Updating of the metaphors supports connection the thinking and its updating	+++		
Visualisation of information: Mapping and Synthesis scaffolding modes			
Good, useful and rich mnemonics	++	Often requires additional prompting to offer mnemonics (protocol needs refinement)	--
		Quality and detail of the MAPs of the TSoI variable	-
Good structured syntheses, following evaluation framework	+++	Poor visual layout of syntheses tables and other synthetic artifacts	-
Ampliative effect of the syntheses (adds nuances and generates new information through increasing reflexivity)	++	Syntheses are sometimes trivial or considered unnecessary when information is limited and they are just “recaps”	-
Organising and reflecting back: Narrative mode of scaffolding			
Offers rich narratives which increase reflexivity and can have multiple uses outside of the interaction	+++	The style of the narrative seems to be influenced by the style of expression of the user. Would be useful to have narrative modes on demand (e.g. journalistic vs. literary)	-

Narratives integrate and elaborate on metaphors expanding the thinking. Ampliative effect of the narratives.	++	
Scaffolding effects		
Effects on the thinking: Inducing reflection, adding new perspectives, organising, stimulating new modes of thinking (e.g. loops); Thought provocation that may continue beyond the session	+++	Requires time (to think and to respond) and may call for several interactions at multiple times
Stimulates and offers support for new interactions and modes of engagement with the TSoI	+++	May generate frustration when only limited amounts of information can be processed (e.g. vs. uploading massive amounts of information)
The user knows the modes available and can take an active role by calling for them and for artifacts	++	The user is not aware of “where they are” in the protocols so as to choose pathways

Following the sessions for cases 5 and 6, we asked the tool to provide a detailed overview of the steps of protocol that were (or were not) followed. It provided a thorough response and justification of where the protocol was adhered to and where there were variations, justifying the adaptations appropriately given the guidance for scaffolding CT and the need to adjust to the team’s cases and nature of the thinking.

In most of the tests, the users engaged with the supporting members of the team, not just asking for technical advice on how to proceed but also to share their thoughts out loud or reflect upon them. Because we did not have a control condition it is not possible to explore the role and effects of this human presence and their impact on the scaffolding process. In cases 5 and 6 there was a discussion between members of the team which was triggered by the questions of the tool. The effects of this discussion are likely to be relevant but the absence of comparative conditions does not allow us to elaborate on them.

In all cases the exploration of the *Relationality* protocols was more limited. For this property, the tool has not been able to generate interesting artifacts (i.e. visual representations that are informative and navigable) that could be used in a mapping mode to record the relational movements performed and the relations identified in the conceptual space that describes the TSoI.

The users and the observation of the tests provided direct and indirect suggestions for improvement and further innovations regarding the protocols and use of the tools. Some of these correspond to adjustments that can be made to current protocols, likely with the result of reducing effort and difficulty such as: (i) allowing the user more choices in regarding the type of syntheses artifacts to be created and the style of the narratives; (ii) allowing the user to choose a style of interaction with the tool (e.g. fact oriented, synthetic and “less polite” interaction vs. friendly, verbose interaction); (iii) providing the user with a map of the scaffolding process allowing them to be aware of which stage they are at and which steps they can “jump” to . This last suggestion poses some dangers as it is necessary to ensure the user does not skip any fundamental stage to build the necessary foundations for being capable of performing CT. Others suggestions may imply more technical challenges and other kinds of interfaces. For example, one user suggested having more texture and levels of interaction i.e. having the option to see all the information but

choose which level to explore in more depth. He also suggested a “learning diary”, where the user could keep a daily record of their thinking stimulated by the tool, with this additional information being used to enrich the interactions. Finally, we believe it is relevant to develop protocols for novice and advanced users to guide them in the use of the tool in a responsible manner, cautioning against the limitations of the current tools for scaffolding CT in relation to the scope of the framework. Other suggestions, like allowing the tool to analyse and respond to large amounts of information are constrained by technical difficulties and the capabilities of the models, like the constraints posed by token limits or the capacity of the tool or user(s) to handle much larger amounts of input information (e.g. data on a target system).

4. Discussion

There is a tendency to consider AI as capable of generating thinking by itself, holding knowledge more advanced than humans, making it seemingly more capable of answering our questions and solving our problems. In other words, there is a trend to endow AI with epistemic authority and decisional sovereignty (Ferrario, Facchini & Termini, 2024; Bartsch et al., 2024). Our main concerns, and the challenges we faced in this project, were related, directly or indirectly, to the preservation of a coupling between humans and the AI that enhances the thinking while safeguarding the user from what we consider a potential epistemic harm in the delegation of their decisions to AI (Malone et al, 2024; Fricker 2007). In designing our tool, we sought to address these challenges: the initial scaffolding questions in the protocol specifically target the observer’s context, clarifying their intentionalities and grounding the thinking in them. Throughout the whole process, we aimed to ensure that decision-making remained in the user’s hands and that any interpretive suggestion by the tool was understood as such — merely a suggestion and a possible interpretation or introduction of a perspective — which could and should be assessed by the user for its pertinence and relevance. This requirement seems to have been met, as evidenced in the tests (e.g. users’ comments on case 4).

We aimed to explore the possibilities of interaction of a CT framework and AI, specifically LLMs, and to develop prompt protocols to scaffold CT. We identified the requirements and challenges for scaffolding CT in ways congruent with the conceptual foundations for the CT framework. We then undertook a staged process of development of the prompt protocols to scaffold a selection of key properties of CT (covering all properties was not feasible in the timeline of the project). The most successful AI models in addressing complex problems use a combination of approaches and the integration of different kinds of models (Marcus & Davis, 2021). We used a combination of modes of engagement and of scaffolding to make the tool more capable of supporting the type of thinking that could address complex problems.

We tested different LLMs guided by a set of criteria that best allowed us to meet the requirements of the framework and assembled a way of organising scaffolding modules, integrating a variety of different modes of scaffolding. We note that all of the tools in this space are undergoing rapid development. In many ways ChatGPT is the most advanced platform. It had certain technical advantages, such as better graphical output, a larger context window and more generous usage limits. However, we kept coming back to Claude. It is interesting to note that Anthropic, the developers of Claude, prioritise maturity and safety: they incorporate a list of rules or principles during the AI training stages, resulting in what they call Constitutional AI (Bai et al, 2022). Moreover, Anthropic employ a philosopher to oversee Claude’s character training (<https://www.anthropic.com/research/claude-character>). Interestingly, Claude is reported to be a favourite amongst people within the tech field, citing its insightful nature and “emotional intelligence” (Roose, 2024). The use of Artifacts (persistent, editable “documents”) afforded by Claude were critical to the success of building a scaffolding tool as they provide a way for the user to actively interact with the outputs of their own thinking in a relatively “instantaneous” and intuitive way.

The protocols were tested and strengths and limitations were identified. Overall, we achieved a positive balance between setting strict boundaries and constraints for the expression of the

capabilities of the models and still ensuring variation and attunement with a tool that combined the Claude Sonnet 3.5 LLM with our protocols. The user's experiences point towards effects that were desirable from the perspective of the CT Framework, despite the current limitations of the tool. We identified key elements of our approach, which led to a scaffolding mode, which in turn relied upon the construction of a robust evaluation mode that could guide the behaviour of the tool and the user. A very detailed step by step algorithmic approach to the guidance and instructions sections of our protocols also allowed us to provide the LLM with a sort of "learner model" and tutorial strategy for an intelligent adaptive tutorial scaffolding system (Sætra, 2022); the general first instructions, the evaluation protocols, the introduction, and appendixes can be regarded as comprising a "teaching module" (Sætra, 2022) on CT, with the LLM providing the dialogical interface.

Another challenge to face is the integration and interaction of the different CT properties, as required by the theoretical framework. Hence, it is not only necessary to develop protocols for other properties of CT but also meta-protocols (and associated tools) to coordinate their interaction and coordination and to choreograph their performance.

Some of our prompts share characteristics with patterns previously identified as effective by other authors, such as White and collaborators (2023), e.g.: reflection patterns (ask the model to explain the rationale of its answers), context manager (specify or remove a context for the conversation), recipe pattern (providing constraints to output a sequence of steps), visualisation generator pattern (use text to create visualisations), template pattern (provide a precise template for structuring an output), cognitive verifier patterns (subdivision of questions into additional questions), or the alternative approaches pattern (ensure LLM offers alternatives to user).

The final protocols presented themselves as satisfactory and, for the targeted properties, seem to lead to desired effects and outcomes. They suggest the viability of developing systems of coupled AI and human intelligences where AIs are "partners in cognition" (Salomon, Perkins & Globerson, 1991) and capable of, at least partially, performing some key scaffolding functions (Sætra, 2022) such as motivation, direction maintenance, simplification, marking critical features and demonstrating, in relation to the performance of CT.

We designed the protocols considering, in particular, the need to scaffold the thinking of a particular observer with a TSoI to afford more complex understandings which could, eventually guide more effective decision-makings and interventions. The tests seemed to provide richer results with users that had a more invested relationship with their TSoI and a concrete context of application/practice where an intervention could take place. At present, we consider that the tool may work better in case-based scenarios, that are more concrete, than for more abstracted levels of thinking, likely as a consequence of grounding the ideas in their particularities, making them more tangible and manipulable. The results provide some support to the idea of distinguishing between the effects of thinking with AI and the effects of AI (Salomon, Perkins & Globerson, 1991); user's reports suggest transformations in patterns of thinking that may be triggered in direct contact with the AI and yet continue to be performed afterward.

The results are encouraging enough to suggest extending the approach to the other properties of the CT framework. However, some challenges remain: for example, the need for better mapping and visualisation of complex information (e.g. multiple levels, multiple degrees of depth and relations) associated with the thinking movements, particularly in support of *Relational Movements*. Our experience, for example, in the Complexigraphy method (Melo & Renault, 2023), shows us the importance of this kind of visual feedback to the user(s) in becoming aware of their patterns of thinking. This current limitation of the tool, we believe is a result of (the then current) technical capabilities of the LLMs, and can be overcome as the platforms become more mature and better integrated with other tools (e.g. network/data visualisations). Moreover, with more resources, a more customised tool could be developed using the LLM API.

Any system to scaffold CT necessarily needs to be open and to support rich and close modes of direct and indirect coupling between the user, their Target System of Interest and their environments. This includes the alignment and ecosystemic fitness of the thinking. This can be

done through key modulating dimensions (e.g. ethical, aesthetic or pragmatic complexity) which are dependent on evaluations and inputs provided by critical observers in such systems. The construction and the valuing of meaning related to the thinking also needs to be retained on the side of the user and other observers in their Target Systems of Interest with whom dialogues need to be established. We also need to explore the possibility of having different modes of interaction and types of interfaces allowing for different types of engagement over time between the user and a tool. For example, designs that support the prompting, producing, managing and integration of the different types of interactions on an “everyday basis” to support and enrich more complex direct couplings of a user with their TSoI and to support an even more dynamic and ongoing unfolding and steering of the thinking. The protocols may benefit from adjustments to create versions for first time and novice users and for more experienced and advanced users. There is also the challenge of designing customised protocols for particular types of Systems and users and to assess differences and similarities of critical processes in different contexts.

Our tests suggest the need to further explore and investigate different configurations of hybrid systems of co-intelligence. For example, the role of a Human Scaffold agent alongside the AI scaffolding role. There is a potential positive role for the mere presence of another human, e.g. to create a favourable emotional environment, increase the confidence and engagement of novice users, as well as to increase reflexivity and to amplify the thinking processes stimulated by the tool. The effects of the use of these tools in teams and the differences between individual and collective uses requires investigation.

5. Conclusion

We aimed at exploring the possibilities and constraints of the interaction of a framework for the practice of CT with AI, specifically LLMs. Our results suggest the viability of using such tools, under well defined constraints set up by a robust evaluation framework and a detailed, narrative and algorithmic prompt protocol to scaffold particular properties of CT of an observer in relation to a TSoI. The quality of the responses of the tools is dependent on particular LLMs, some of which may be more or less congruent with the aim of scaffolding CT. The protocols developed encompass a variety of modes of scaffolding and use the capabilities of the LLMs aiming to achieve a balance of keeping within the bounds of the CT framework, while adapting to the user’s context, and adding new information. Many technical challenges remain to be overcome, in particular the development of meta-tools to support the coordination and integration, orchestration or choreographing (Melo & Renault, 2023) of CT. Some challenges may be naturally overcome due to developments in the LLMs. Others may require the combination and integration of a variety of technologies and types of AI but also sophisticated protocols for the assemblage of systems with different configurations of co-augmented intelligences (Melo, 2022), e.g. incorporating (i) multiple users/observers (e.g. teams), attending and facilitating the complexity of their own coupling and (ii) the coordination of other human and AI Scaffolders. The possibilities are vast and as the systems for scaffolding CT evolve so may our understanding of the scaffolding and the performance of CT itself, eventually to the point where it more directly plays a role in the training of AIs themselves.

6. Data availability

Data referring to this study (e.g. logs of chats, transcriptions of sessions, databases of questions, transcripts of interviews, history of protocols) as well as the final suite of protocols can be found in the community Complex Thinking & AI at the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/ctai>) and Github under the Complex Thinking Initiative (<https://github.com/complexthinking>) in the specific repository for the Complex Thinking & AI project (<https://github.com/complexthinking/complexthinkingai>).

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8. Authors' statements

The authors adhere to an adapted version of the CRediT author statement (Allen, O'Connell, and Kiermer 2019) to recognise individual contributions:

Ana Teixeira de Melo: Conceptualisation; methodology; software; data analysis; investigation; data curation; writing-original draft (major); visualisation; supervision; project administration; funding acquisition

Leticia Renault: Conceptualisation; methodology, software; data analysis; investigation; data-curation; writing-original draft (major);

Leo Caves: Methodology; Software; data analysis; investigation; writing-original draft (major); visualisation

Philip Garnett: Software; investigation; writing-original draft (minor)

Paula Duarte Lopes: Investigation;

Raquel Ribeiro: Investigation; writing-review & editing

Filipe Santos: Investigation; writing-review & editing

Appendix A. List of protocols

A protocol suite was developed to Scaffold Complex Thinking in terms of the Dimension of Structural Complexity, and its properties of Structural Variety and Dimensionality and Relationality. The following protocols were integrated and fine-tuned for Claude Sonnet 3.5 (information between squared brackets refers to the identifiers associated with the protocols):

1. GENERAL FIRST INSTRUCTIONS [SC.SVD.REL. GENERAL FIRST INSTRUCTIONS_EVAL AND SCAFFOLDING] protocol, to be inserted into projects (containing different versions of the text, depending which of the other protocols are used) (3 p.);
2. Evaluation of Structural Complexity/Structural Variety and Dimensionality [SC.SVD. EVALUATING STRUCTURAL VARIETY AND DIMENSIONALITY] (5 p.);
3. Scaffolding Structural Complexity/Structural Variety and Dimensionality [SC.SVD. SCAFFOLDING STRUCTURAL VARIETY AND DIMENSIONALITY] (16p.);
4. Evaluation of Structural Complexity/Relationality [SC.REL_EVAL_ EVALUATING RELATIONALITY] (8p.);
5. Scaffolding Structural Complexity/Relationality/Relations as Entities [SC.REL. R. SCAFFOLDING RELATIONS] (8p.);
6. Scaffolding Structural Complexity/Relationality/Relational Movements [SC.REL.RM. SCAFFOLDING RELATIONAL MOVEMENTS] (8p.).
7. Integrated Evaluation and Scaffolding of Relationality, Relations and Entities and Relational Movements [SC.REL.RE.RM.EVALUATING AND SCAFFOLDING RELATIONALITY] (14 p.)

Appendix B. Context, purpose and highlights of case studies

Case 1: int.user#1

Context/purpose. The user had a theoretical-applied research problem. He was experienced with AI. He operated at the intersection of academic research and the justice and mental health system by analysing and consulting on the decisions related to the execution of security measures by mentally disordered offenders. He was aiming to have insights on the subject. There were several test sessions, continuing the same chat.

Negative highlights of the interaction. The outputs were sometimes considered “*verbose*”.

Positive Highlights of the interaction. i. Experience of a “*natural*” dialogue; ii. “*Enjoyable experience*”; iii. First quite good experience with radial maps (improved after this test); iv. Interesting mnemonics were created; v. Notes mode was very active. Tool identified insights in the user and proposed to use [NOTES MODE]; vi. Return to Relationality after a session break requires a “warm-up” and procedural questions stage; vii. Interaction, particularly the Relationality triggered new insights and perspectives; viii. Presence of the team possibly made the non-linearity of the dialogue more manageable and enjoyable than with an individual exploration; ix. Syntheses were considered useful (“*It's very, very interesting to see this whole information synthesized in a single page. It's very helpful*”)

Case 2: int.user#2

Context/purpose. The user works in the domain of social psychology. She was inexperienced with AI. She had a theoretical research problem focused on housing issues. She was interested in understanding how to enrich her research from a Complex Thinking perspective. There were several test sessions, opening new chats on each occasion.

Negative highlights of the interaction. i. The user was “*impatient*” with the tool. User did not wish to answer nor write down detailed responses to questions or to repeat “information she already knew” but wanted feedback on her own work and suggestions for improvement, resulting in sometimes frustrating experience; ii. User wished to upload large amounts of information (e.g. book written on the issue) and have feedback from that but it rapidly used up token limits for the day and shortened the interaction; iii. User deviated frequently from the protocol avoiding the direct questions of the tool; iv. User found having to write responses “*tiring*” and would have preferred oral interaction

Positive Highlights of the interaction. i. Questions considered interesting, stimulating new ideas; ii. Sometimes “*exciting*” experience.

Case 3: ext.user#1

Context/purpose. The user was experienced with AI. He is a researcher interested in Futures research. He defined his topic and system of interest as “*uncertainties of the future of work*”.

Negative highlights of the interaction. i. Outputs were sometimes considered “*verbose*”; ii. User would prefer identifiers to be hidden; iii. Mapping felt as a bit “*too obvious*” but still helpful (“*Documenting, not really adding anything. (...) But it but it helps. OK*”); iv. Problem was too abstract. Could benefit from concrete examples (which was suggested by the tool); v. Sometimes questions perceived as “*too massive*” i.e. difficult to respond to immediately.

Positive Highlights of the interaction. i. Metaphor exploration was well-received and useful, interpretations are close to user meanings but offer new perspectives (“*yes, very good, catalyst of change [tool offered interpretation of the metaphor] I like that (...) yes, this is nicely mapping out what I've been thinking in different ways, this is good*”); ii. Positive experience of novelty and insights introduced through the Relationality/Relational Movements (“*for me this part is more interesting, to get new perspectives and new starting points and then to connect them*”; “*Actually, it's interesting because it's inviting you to think about them the other way around*”); iii. Appreciation of how tool “*keeps track of everything and brings them together*”. There is an indication of a more comprehensive and inclusive view of the problem, which integrates various

elements, thereby facilitating not only relational movements but also a more visual organization of information. There is an appreciation of its ability to maintain an overview of complex information. ; iv. Appreciation of the questions (“*the questions are quite good*”; “*yes, I think these are good statements*”); v. Questions were well adapted to context (“*it’s just doing that on its own. This is perfect then*”); vi. Appreciation of embodied focus (“*yeah, yeah, it’s good*”); vii. Experience of recursive thinking loops (“*It’s making me think of a kind of a loop now*”); viii. Team experience that they were the ones doing the thinking, and that their curiosity was stimulated, and they were engaged, supported by the tool (“*yes, that [it] makes us think. It is indeed very interesting, very complementary and challenging, but at the time it is structuring (...) truly provokes in us, I want to know more, let me see now what you are going to say, how we can do this [implement the suggested activities] What can I do with the family?*”)

Case 4: ext.user#2

Context/purpose. User was inexperienced with AI. She is a researcher working with socio-ecological problems. She defined her problem as “how the sociopolitical dimension of nature-based solutions can be explored using complex thinking tools”.

Negative highlights of the interaction. i. User had expectations that her questions would be answered; ii. Glitch: too many questions presented at once, although corrected later on; iii. Some modes were skipped. User’s discourse somehow prompted to go to “Relationality” too early

Positive Highlights of the interaction. i. User had insights of new ideas (“*great to think about*”); ii. User appreciated suggestions of activities to carry on. iii. User engaged in a critical evaluation of the questions and didn’t take the information for granted (“*I think this question, it’s better than the other, because there are some of these elements more influential than others in shaping the best outcomes. I think this is a great point to think about it*”). There is a sense of thought provocation that does not appear to conclude with the interaction with the protocol but promises to continue over an extended period.

Case 5: ext.user#3

Context/purpose. A team of two users of community-based family support practitioners conducted the test focused on a case conceptualisation of a family with at-risk children. The team had two separate sessions, the second on Relationality.

Negative highlights of the interaction. i. The transition between protocols in the two different sessions was perceived as “cold”, lacking the “warming-up” and focus on building a connection with the case of the first session on the Structural Variety and Dimensionality protocol; ii. The tables layout was poor and uninteresting (“*but it is a shame it was not in a [proper] table format*”)

Positive Highlights of the interaction. i. The unpacking and exploration conducted by the tool of the metaphor proposed by the team was considered as “highly potent” and “an excellent resource to use with the family”, likewise the narratives (in literary-style) that were produced based on the metaphor (“*it can be a very useful intervention tool with the family (...) I believe this will have a very positive impact on her*”); ii. Synthesis of information, including in the tables was considered useful despite the poor layout (“*the information is well synthesised in topics, which guides the organisation*”). The way the synthesis is organised and feeds back information adds something new (but close) to the thinking of the team (“*I thought the same magic happened a moment ago, this and that. I really liked the synthesis (...) It is a way for us, new to an immediate situation, to receive a very well-organised synthesis [when sometime the thinking still isn’t] which we then use for information; it is true, but we receive the information organised, so it is ,wow!*”, “*besides the bullet point referencing the tool created a relating by areas, which organises the information and guides the way we are thinking the case, amplifying our perspective*”, “*gives us a perspective of what is missing*”) iii. “Natural” interaction and engaging coupling and “game-like” interaction (“*it happens in an almost natural way, doesn’t it? We become involved, don’t we? So now it’s a question [posed by the tool], now I do it this way. And it was something very fluid, isn’t*”)

it? Something that almost then emerged in a very natural way. And I didn't feel the weight of [the technology].

Note: Although we developed the protocols in English, the users interacted with the tool in Portuguese. The results were positive.

Case 6: ext.user#4

Context/purpose. A team of two users of community-based family support practitioners conducted the test focused on a case conceptualisation of a family with at-risk children. The team had two separate sessions, the second on Relationality.

Negative highlights of the interaction. i. Same as case 5.

Positive Highlights of the interaction. i. The team appreciated and used the [NOTES MODE] frequently; ii. The questions posed by the tool triggered discussions between the team members generating a variety of complementary perspectives. The team presented these diverse perspectives back to the tool for exploration; iii. The team frequently used the team member supporting the test as another scaffolding and reflexive partner and discussing their choices with her; iv. The metaphors and reports were highly valued, enriching the thinking (*"it was very good, it was very enriching. The spectacular metaphors, the way it...(did it)"*); iv. Productive and enriching experience; v. The way the tool fills in and adds what is not explicitly said (but was implicit in the text and in the metaphor chosen) (*"I found it to be very productive. Thank you,, thank you as well. Thank you, we understand so many aspects. Thank you, goodness. We write and don't write everything. And the way he manages to read what we are writing, I found spectacular. And believing that what we did not say ended up being reflected in the resolutions that the program was making."*).

Note: The users' natural language is Portuguese. They interacted with the tool in English using a translator app on their browser. Although we developed the protocols in English, the users interacted with the tool in Portuguese. The results were positive.

Appendix C. Illustrative excerpts from chat logs for the case studies**Illustrative excerpts for Case 1: int.user#1**

<i>Early stage of the dialogue introducing procedural questions</i>	
Participant	Excerpt of the chat log
AI/Claude	<p>Excellent. Let's begin with Phase 0, which aims to clarify procedures and language.</p> <p>[PHASE 0] [STEP 0.1]</p> <p>I'll use the [PROCEDURAL QUESTIONS] from Appendix A to confirm and clarify the working conditions for our scaffolding session.</p> <p>PQ1. Would you like to have a small introduction tutorial on key terms that we could use to structure our conversation?</p> <p>PQ2. I propose to call your problem/concern/question "the Target System of Interest (TSoI)". If you would like to call it something different, please tell me.</p> <p>Could you please respond to these procedural questions so we can establish a clear foundation for our scaffolding process?</p>
User	My relation is as a consultant/advisory to a court
AI/Claude	<p>Thank you for sharing that information about your relation to the TSoI. Let's continue with the next foundational modulating question to further explore your perspective.</p> <p>[SC.SVD.MD.O.MOD.OC.MP.FMODQ2] What are your intentions in relation to your TSoI? What would you like to achieve? For example, would you like to build (i) a comprehensive description, (ii) explanations, (iii) anticipations of predictions (e.g. of what could happen if nothing or something changes or possible effects of interventions)?</p>
User	I am trying to make a decision on whether an individual diagnosed with a mental disorder, currently compensated, should be eligible for parole.
AI/Claude	<p>Thank you for clarifying your intention. This helps us understand the context and complexity of your TSoI. Let's continue with the next question to further explore your perspective.</p> <p>[SC.SVD.MD.O.MOD.OC.MP.FMODQ3] What is important or interesting to you in relation to your TSoI?</p>

User	It is important to know: 1. if the individual will maintain treatment; 2. if the community is prepared and willing to accept him.
AI/Claude	Thank you for sharing these important aspects of your TSoI. Your focus on treatment maintenance and community preparedness shows a consideration for both the individual and the broader social context. Let's move to the final foundational modulating question to complete our initial exploration. [SC.SVD.MD.O.MOD.OC.MP.FMODQ4] What are the values guiding your interaction and intentions in relation to your TSoI?
User	My values consider the overall common good. That is, to regard the individual's rights (to liberty and autonomy), while protecting the community concerns for safety.
Asking for the first metaphor [METAPHOR MODE]	
AI/Claude	Thank you for articulating the values guiding your interaction with the TSoI. Your focus on balancing individual rights with community safety demonstrates a nuanced approach to this complex situation. Now that we've completed the foundational modulating questions, I'd like to help you think of a metaphor that best represents the nature of your relation with the TSoI. [METAPHOR MODE] Can you think of a metaphor (e.g., an image, a word, a sound, an object, or a movement) that captures the nature of how you are thinking about this decision-making process regarding the individual's eligibility for parole?
User	So, you have a wolf that has been trained and is being adopted by a family that has other animals, like dogs and cats, but also livestock. Can we trust the training, or that the wolf will come out, eventually?
Unpacking and exploring the metaphor on [METAPHOR MODE]	
AI/Claude	Thank you for sharing this powerful metaphor. It effectively captures the complexity and potential risks involved in your decision-making process. Let's create a visual representation of this metaphor.

	<p style="text-align: center;">Wolf Integration Dilemma</p> <p>This visual representation captures the key elements of your metaphor:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The wolf (representing the individual with a mental disorder) is shown as larger and separate from the other animals, symbolizing its potential threat and the uncertainty of its integration.2. The family is represented by a house, with various animals (dogs, cats, and livestock) nearby, symbolizing the community.3. A fence separates the wolf from the family and other animals, representing the current separation and the potential for integration.4. The sky and grass background represent the broader environment in which this situation is taking place. <p>This metaphor effectively illustrates several key aspects of your TSoI:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The trained wolf represents the individual diagnosed with a mental disorder who is currently compensated.2. The training of the wolf mirrors the treatment the individual has received.3. The family adopting the wolf represents the community that would be accepting the individual back.4. The other animals (dogs, cats, livestock) represent different members of the community with varying levels of vulnerability.5. The question of trusting the training or the potential for the wolf's nature to "come out eventually" directly relates to your concerns about whether the individual will maintain treatment and whether the community is prepared for potential risks. <p>This metaphor encapsulates the balance you're trying to strike between the individual's rights (the wolf's chance at a new life) and community safety</p>
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	<p>(protecting the family and other animals). It also highlights the uncertainty and potential risks involved in your decision.</p> <p>Now that we have this metaphor to work with, let's move on to [PHASE 2] to further explore different dimensions of the complexity of your thinking about this TSoI.</p>
Initiating foundational questions in Dialogical Scaffolding mode [DSCAFF]	
AI/Claude	<p>[PHASE 2] [STEP 2.1] I'll now guide you through a series of [FOUNDATIONAL QUESTIONS] to help you reflect on different dimensions of the complexity of your thinking. We'll start with the first question: [SC.SVD.MD.IC.FQ1] Please provide an initial description of your Target System of Interest (TSoI), considering its basic elements, such as types of individuals and groups as well as other types of beings, existing hierarchies and levels of organization among them, nature of their interactions and relations, different functions and purposes supported by these elements, patterns of the TSoI and how they relate back to the elements, narratives and preferred identities of the TSoI.</p>
	<i>[Because of a glitch the AI did not confirm the metaphor before proceeding. The user calls for improvements]</i>
User	Can you use objects instead of geometric shapes?
AI/Claude	Of course! I apologize for the abstract representation. Let's create a more concrete visual representation of your metaphor using objects instead of geometric shapes.
	(...) [RESUMING FOUNDATIONAL QUESTIONS AFTER IMPROVING METAPHOR REPRESENTATION]
AI/Claude	Now, let's return to our foundational question. Could you please provide an initial description of your Target System of Interest (TSoI), considering its basic elements, individuals, groups, their interactions, and the overall patterns and narratives involved in this parole decision scenario?

	Illustration of scaffolding questions
Participant	The individual is a male, under 30, suffering from schizophrenia, that received a security measure because he murdered his brother.
AI/Claude	[CONTINUING SCAFFOLDING WITH FOUNDATIONAL QUESTIONS]

	<p>Thank you for providing this specific information about the individual in your Target System of Interest (TSoI). This gives us a clearer picture of the complexity involved. Let's continue to build on this description with the next foundational question:</p> <p>[SC.SVD.MD.E.FQ2] Please provide a description of the social, material, cultural, institutional and natural environment of TSoI.</p> <p>Could you describe the environment in which this decision is being made? This could include aspects such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The institutional context (e.g., the court system, mental health facilities) ● The social and cultural context of the community where he might be released ● Any relevant laws or policies that govern this decision ● The available support systems or resources for individuals with mental health conditions in the community
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	<p>Reminding the user on the possibility of using [NOTES MODE]</p>
<p>AI/Claude</p>	<p>Also, I'd like to remind you that during our interaction and the scaffolding process, you're encouraged to pay attention to ideas that come to your mind and their potential relevance for understanding your TSoI. Try to "think with your whole body" and pay attention to your reactions, emotions, or even vague impressions. At any moment, you can ask me to make a note of these ideas and impressions by activating the [NOTES MODE]. Just let me know if you want to do this at any point.</p> <p>Are you ready to proceed with the scaffolding process?</p>

	<p>Scaffolding Relationality/Relational as Entities</p>
<p>AI/Claude</p>	<p>Now, let's consider how these aspects relate to other elements in our TSoI: [SC.RL.R.F.Q3] How can the relations between the key elements in your Target System of Interest (TSoI) be described? What other types of relational descriptions, qualifiers and types, dimensions or properties of relations can be considered?</p> <p>Considering the emotional well-being aspect you've brought up, how would you describe its relationship to other key elements we've discussed (such as</p>

	<p>medication management, family support, community perceptions)? Are there any new types of relations or properties that come to mind when considering emotional well-being?</p>
<p>User</p>	<p>Well, emotional well-being could support relations with the environment, namely, by easing the social stigma and integration into community groups. In the long term, I believe it would benefit rehabilitation perspectives.</p>
<p>AI/Claude</p>	<p>Excellent observation. You've identified an important relationship between emotional well-being and several other key elements of the TSoI. Let's explore this further:</p> <p>[SC.RL.R.F.Q4] Are there any patterns or structures that emerge from these relations?</p> <p>Your insight suggests a potential pattern: emotional well-being as a facilitator for other positive outcomes. This could form a structure where emotional well-being is at the center, influencing various other aspects of the TSoI's life and rehabilitation. Let's visualize this:</p> <p>This diagram illustrates the central role of emotional well-being and its bidirectional relationships with other key elements of the TSoI.</p> <p>Now, let's delve deeper into these relationships:</p> <p>[SC.RL.R.F.Q5] How do different types of relations interact and influence each other? Are there relations between relations? How do changes in one relation affect other relations within the TSoI?</p> <p>For example, how might improvements in the TSoI's emotional well-being affect his relationship with his family, and how might that, in turn, impact his medication adherence or community integration? Can you identify any potential chain reactions or feedback loops in these relationships?</p>

Offering a mnemonic [SYNTH MODE] after an evaluation of Relationality [Relations as

Entities and Relational Movements] followed by an updated map of the thinking [TSOI MAP]	
User	Can you give a easy to memorise version of this?
AI/Claude	<p>Certainly. I'll provide a concise, easy-to-memorize version of the relationality evaluation using a simple framework.</p> <p>[ARTIFACT] # TIES Relationality Summary</p> <p>## T - Threads: Multiple interconnected relationships - Illness insight and emotional well-being form the central thread - Many threads connect various aspects (family, treatment, community)</p> <p>## I - Integration: Holistic view of the TSoI's situation - Different elements are woven together cohesively - Changes in one area ripple through the entire system</p> <p>## E - Exploration: Dynamic investigation of relationships - Circular thinking examines how factors influence each other - Considers both immediate and long-term effects of relationships</p> <p>## S - Sophistication: High complexity in relational thinking - Qualifies relationships (e.g., "deeply intertwined") - Identifies relationships between relationships</p> <p>Remember: The narrative TIES together multiple threads, integrates various elements, explores dynamic relationships, and shows sophistication in relational thinking.</p> <p>This TIES framework provides an easy-to-remember summary of the key aspects of relationality in your updated narrative:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Threads remind you of the multiple interconnected relationships you've identified. 2. Integration highlights how you've woven different elements together into a cohesive whole. 3. Exploration emphasizes the dynamic nature of your relational thinking. 4. Sophistication underscores the high level of complexity in your consideration of relationships. <p>By remembering TIES, you can quickly recall the main strengths of your relational thinking about the TSoI. This framework also provides a quick checklist for maintaining and further developing the complexity of your relational thinking in future analyses.</p>
User	Can you give me an updated map of my thinking?
AI/Claude	Certainly. I'll create an updated map of your thinking based on our recent discussions, particularly incorporating the central role of illness insight and

emotional well-being, as well as the various relationships we've explored.
 [ARTIFACT: Updated TSoI Thinking Map]

This updated map of your thinking about the TSoI reflects the increased complexity and relationality we've discussed. Here are the key features:

1. Central TSoI: The young male with schizophrenia remains at the center.
2. Core Focus Area: Illness Insight and Emotional Well-being are now highlighted as a core focus area, represented by the dashed ellipse encompassing the central TSoI.
3. Four Main Dimensions:
 - 1.A Internal Complexity (right)
 - 1.B Environment (left)
 - 1.C Observer (top)
 - 1.D Coupling (bottom)
4. Sub-elements: Each main dimension has relevant sub-elements, reflecting the depth of consideration for each aspect.
5. Relationships: Arrows indicate the relationships between different elements, with a focus on how the core area of Illness Insight and

	<p>Emotional Well-being connects to other dimensions.</p> <p>This map visualizes several key aspects of your thinking:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The centrality of illness insight and emotional well-being in your understanding of the TSoI's situation. ● The interconnectedness of various elements, showing how changes in one area might affect others. ● The balance between internal factors (symptom management, medication adherence) and external factors (family dynamics, community integration). ● The role of the observer (court consultant) in assessing and potentially influencing the system. ● The coupling between treatment effectiveness and rehabilitation progress. <p>This visualization captures the TIES framework we discussed earlier:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Threads: Multiple interconnected relationships are shown by the arrows. ● Integration: The central focus area integrates with all other dimensions. ● Exploration: The layout suggests dynamic relationships between elements. ● Sophistication: The inclusion of sub-elements and multiple relationships demonstrates the complexity of your thinking. <p>This map serves as a visual summary of your current thinking about the TSoI, highlighting the complex, relational nature of your analysis. Indicates how these aspects of the observer's role are related.</p>
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<p>Illustration of a response to a user’s direct request for a solution from within the framework and returning to the dialogical scaffolding mode [DSCAFF], offering suggestions as possibilities alongside questions</p>	
User	<p>Let me take you aside. How would you organize a system to care for not criminally responsible patients, in the described context?</p>
AI/Claude	<p>Thank you for this thought-provoking question. To address this, let's consider a systemic approach that takes into account the complex relationships we've discussed. I'll outline a potential organizational structure, and then we can explore how it might address the issues we've identified.</p> <p>[SC.REL.RM.SCAFF.Q18] To what extent could these relata be integrated or explained by a larger or higher-order entity or dimensions or be related at the level of their parts?</p>

	<p>Consider this potential organizational system:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Integrated Assessment Centers:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Multidisciplinary teams including legal experts, psychiatrists, psychologists, and social workers.- Conduct comprehensive evaluations to determine both legal status and medical needs.2. Specialized Treatment Facilities:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Separate units for different types of conditions (e.g., one for schizophrenia, another for brain injuries).- Staff trained in both legal implications and medical treatment of specific conditions.3. Tiered Insight Development Program:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Tailored programs to develop illness insight based on cognitive capabilities and specific conditions.- Regular reassessments to adjust legal status and treatment plans.4. Integrated Legal-Medical Review Boards:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Regular case reviews by a board of both legal and medical professionals.- Ensures ongoing alignment between legal status and medical treatment.5. Transitional Care Units:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Bridge the gap between secure facilities and community reintegration.- Focus on practical application of illness insight and management.6. Continuing Education Program:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- For staff across all units to stay updated on both legal and medical developments.- Promotes a culture of integrated legal-medical understanding. <p>Now, let's explore how this system might address the relationships we've discussed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. How might this integrated approach affect the development of illness insight in patients with different conditions?2. In what ways could this system better balance legal requirements with medical needs?3. How might this structure influence the relationship between healthcare providers' approaches and patients' understanding of their conditions?4. How could this system potentially resolve some of the tensions we identified between legal categories and medical treatment approaches?5. In what ways might this organizational structure itself emerge as a new factor in the relationship between illness insight and the healthcare system?
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Illustrative excerpts for Case 2: int.user#2

<p>Illustration of visual synthesis map after the production of a narrative</p>	
<p>AI/Claude</p>	<p>Excellent. I'm glad the narrative accurately reflects your understanding of the housing crisis in Portugal. Let's move forward with our analysis. [STEP 2.3] Now, I'd like to offer you a synthesis of the information we've generated so far. Synthesis: Housing Crisis in Portugal [ARTIFACT]</p> <p>I've created a mind map to synthesize the key elements of the housing crisis in Portugal. This visual representation aims to capture the main components and their relationships within the system. The mind map is organized around the central concept of the "Housing Crisis in Portugal" and branches out into the main categories we've discussed: Basic Elements, Hierarchies, Interactions, Functions, Patterns, and Narratives. Each of these branches further subdivides into more specific elements. This synthesis can help in visualizing the complexity of the system and the interrelations between its various components. It can also serve as a quick reference for the key aspects of the housing crisis. Would you like me to explain any part of this synthesis in more detail? Or shall we move on to the next phase of our analysis?</p>
<p>User</p>	<p>Thank you. Let's continue</p>
	<p>Certainly, let's continue with our analysis and move on to the next phase.</p>

Illustration of a follow-up explanation of the evaluation provided	
AI/Claude	(following presenting an evaluation and a TSoI_TABLE) Would you like me to explain any part of this evaluation in more detail?
User	Yes
AI/Claude	<p>Certainly. I'll explain each part of the evaluation in more detail:</p> <p>[TSoI_TABLE]: This table maps the contents of your thinking onto four key dimensions: a) Internal Complexity of TSoI (1.A): This is the most developed dimension in your narrative. It includes a rich description of basic elements (like residents, landlords, investors), hierarchies (government levels, economic strata), interactions (mortgage lending, property renting), functions (shelter provision, income generation), patterns (financialization, rising prices), and narratives (homeownership aspiration, housing as a human right). b) Environment of TSoI (1.B): This dimension is less developed. While you implicitly reference economic conditions and cultural values, there's limited explicit description of broader environmental factors that influence the housing crisis. c) Observer (1.C): This dimension includes your role as a social psychology researcher, your intentions to build comprehensive descriptions and explanations, and your values of fairness, inclusivity, and sustainability. d) Coupling (1.D): This dimension is the least developed, with limited explicit description of how the system, environment, and observer interact.</p> <p>Sub-properties Evaluation: a) Multidimensionality and Variety of Contents [MDV]: Rated as Moderate complexity. Your narrative covers three out of four dimensions (internal complexity, observer, and some environment) with high thematic variety in the internal complexity. However, the environment and coupling dimensions are less developed. b) Depth of Information: Rated as Moderate complexity. You provide various types of information (structural, functional, narrative), but the sources of information are not explicitly varied. c) Nature of Contents: Rated as Moderate complexity. Your narrative balances individual and relational entities, and atomic and configurational descriptions. However, it leans more towards abstract descriptions with fewer concrete examples. d) Framing the Information: Rated as Moderate complexity. The information is somewhat contextualized (e.g., mentioning changes since the 1990s, urban vs. rural differences) and adds meaning to understanding the TSoI. However, more detailed spatial and temporal contextualization could enhance this aspect.</p> <p>Overall Evaluation: Your thinking demonstrates moderate complexity. It excels in describing the internal complexity of the system with a rich variety of elements, interactions, and patterns. To increase complexity, you could: Explicitly address the broader environment of the system (e.g., global economic trends, climate change impacts on housing) Describe the coupling between system components, the environment, and yourself as an observer Provide more concrete, situated examples to balance the abstract descriptions Explicitly mention diverse sources of information</p> <p>Is there any specific part of this evaluation you'd like me to elaborate on further?</p>

Illustration of suggestion of activities [ACTIVE SCAFFOLDING] for theoretical problem of housing	
AI/Claude	<p>[STEP 3.4] Given that we've explored the environment dimension to some extent, I'd like to offer you the opportunity to engage in some active scaffolding to potentially increase the complexity of your thinking and produce novel information on your Target System of Interest (TSOI). Would you like some suggestions for activities that could help you further develop your understanding of the housing crisis in Portugal, particularly focusing on the environmental aspects we've been discussing? These activities could help you generate new insights or connections, especially in areas that are less developed in your current thinking, such as the broader global context and its interaction with local factors. If you're interested, I can suggest a few activities. If not, we can move on to the next phase of our analysis. What would you prefer?</p>
User	<p>Yes, Please suggest a few activities</p>
AI/Claude	<p>Certainly! I'm glad you're open to some activities to further develop your understanding of the housing crisis in Portugal, particularly focusing on the environmental aspects. Here are a few suggestions: Active Scaffolding Activities: Housing Crisis in Portugal [ARTIFACT] [ACTIVE TSOI MODE]</p> <p>Active Scaffolding Activities: Housing Crisis in Portugal 1. Global-Local Mapping Exercise Create a visual map that illustrates the connections between global financialization trends and local housing markets in Portugal.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use a large sheet of paper or a digital mind-mapping tool. ● In the center, place "Portuguese Housing Crisis". ● On one side, list global factors (e.g., international investment trends, global economic policies). ● On the other side, list local factors (e.g., local housing policies, demographic changes). ● Draw lines connecting these factors to the central topic, using different colors or line styles to represent different types of influences (direct, indirect, strong, weak). ● Add brief notes explaining each connection. <p>This activity can help visualize the complex interplay between global and local factors, potentially revealing new connections or areas for further research.</p> <p>2. Stakeholder Perspective Analysis Conduct a role-playing exercise to explore different stakeholder perspectives on the housing crisis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify 5-7 key stakeholders (e.g., international investor, local

	<p>resident, policymaker, social housing advocate, real estate developer).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For each stakeholder, write a brief (1-2 paragraph) statement from their perspective about the housing situation in Portugal. ● Consider their motivations, concerns, and how they might view other stakeholders. ● After writing these, compare and contrast the perspectives. Look for areas of conflict and potential common ground. <p>This activity can help develop a more nuanced understanding of the various interests at play in the housing crisis, potentially revealing new angles for policy approaches or research questions.</p> <p>3. Historical Timeline Construction Create a timeline of key events and policies related to housing in Portugal, with a focus on how they interact with global trends.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Start from a significant point in the past (e.g., Portugal's entry into the EU) up to the present. ● Include both local events/policies and global economic milestones. ● For each entry, briefly note its impact on housing affordability or accessibility. ● Look for patterns or turning points where global and local factors intersect. <p>This activity can help identify historical trends and pivotal moments that have shaped the current housing crisis, potentially revealing long-term patterns or cycles that could inform future predictions or policy recommendations.</p> <p>4. Comparative Case Study Select 2-3 other countries or cities facing similar housing challenges and conduct a brief comparative analysis with Portugal.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Choose locations with some similarities to Portugal (e.g., in size, economic situation, or housing market structure). ● For each case, summarize key aspects: housing market trends, policy approaches, social impacts. ● Create a table or matrix comparing these factors across the cases. ● Identify unique aspects of Portugal's situation as well as common threads. <p>This activity can provide a broader context for Portugal's housing crisis, potentially revealing alternative approaches or unique factors in the Portuguese case that might not be apparent when studying it in isolation. These activities are designed to engage with the environmental aspects of the housing crisis in Portugal, encouraging you to make new connections and generate novel insights. They address areas that were less developed in your initial description, such as global-local interactions and historical contexts.</p> <p>___ [END ARTIFACT] I've suggested four activities that could help you further develop your</p>
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	<p>understanding of the housing crisis in Portugal, with a focus on environmental factors:</p> <p>Global-Local Mapping Exercise Stakeholder Perspective Analysis Historical Timeline Construction Comparative Case Study</p> <p>Each of these activities is designed to help you explore different aspects of the housing crisis, particularly focusing on the interaction between global and local factors, diverse stakeholder perspectives, historical context, and comparative analysis.</p> <p>These activities aim to increase the complexity of your thinking by encouraging you to:</p> <p>Visualize complex relationships Consider multiple perspectives Analyze historical trends and their impacts Compare Portugal's situation with other contexts</p> <p>Would you like me to explain any of these activities in more detail? Or do you have a preference for which activity you'd like to focus on?</p>
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Illustration of Dialogical Scaffolding, selecting and adjusting questions to context	
User	<p>Thank you Claude. The main alternative approach is considering that the housing crisis is a crisis of lack of houses. Housing is unaffordable because the construction of houses is low and therefore the low offer leads to high prices</p>
AI/Claude	<p>Thank you for sharing this important alternative perspective. It's a significant contrast to the financialization-focused view you presented earlier. Let's explore this further.</p> <p>[SC.SVD.MD.MOD.OC.MP.SCAFFMODQ6]</p> <p>Given this alternative perspective that the housing crisis is primarily a supply issue, who would you identify as the critical observers or entities implicated in the housing crisis in Portugal? Please identify all the key stakeholders, including those who might hold this alternative view of a supply shortage.</p> <p>Consider including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Those who advocate for increased construction ● Those who focus on financialization ● Government officials at various levels ● Construction industry representatives ● Urban planners ● Economists with different viewpoints ● Affected residents (both homeowners and renters) ● Any other key groups you think are relevant <p>How do these different groups contribute to or are affected by the housing crisis?</p>

Illustrative excerpts for Case 3: ext.user#1

Illustration of Narrative Mode integrating previous metaphor (trickster)	
AI/Claude	<p>Based on our dialogue, I'll create a narrative that captures how you're thinking about your TSoI. After I present it, please let me know if you'd like to make any amendments or if it accurately reflects your thinking so far.</p> <p># Narrative: Uncertainties of the Future of Work</p> <p>The exploration of the uncertainties in the future of work is a complex and multifaceted endeavor, characterized by the interplay of various actors, spaces, and evolving concepts of value and meaning. This Target System of Interest (TSoI) is approached from the perspective of a researcher who, while not an expert, is deeply engaged with the topic and seeks to facilitate meaningful discussions about possible futures.</p> <p>Key elements of this TSoI include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Actors: Workers, non-workers, and others, including potential influencers like policymakers and technology developers. 2. Spaces of Work: A spectrum from neutral, flexible spaces to structured, potentially controlling environments. The concept of work spaces is being redefined by factors such as seasonal work, night work, and day work. 3. Value and Meaning of Work: These are in constant flux, influenced by changing social norms and external factors like environmental and political influences. 4. Environmental Factors: Climate change is increasingly shaping the future of work, potentially leading to radical shifts such as nocturnal work schedules in hotter climates. 5. Cultural and Social Responses: Adaptability and resilience are key themes, with examples like Cuba's social response to power outages highlighting the potential for reimagining work-life integration. 6. Institutional and Material Aspects: There's a noted tension between slow institutional adaptation and the need for rapid change in response to environmental and social shifts. <p>The approach to this TSoI is characterized by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A 'trickster' mentality that challenges established assumptions and introduces unpredictability. 2. A focus on human skills, relationships, and agency in the face of technological changes. 3. A critical stance towards current work structures, combined with willing participation in them. 4. An emphasis on seeing alternatives and embracing the tension between dualities.

	<p>5. A view of the unknown future as both a possibility and a threat, balanced with the recognition that current knowledge and experiences can guide engagement with uncertainty.</p> <p>The ultimate aim is to explore scenarios and anticipate new realms to aid critical discussion on the current state of affairs, with a particular emphasis on valuing human aspects over technological fixes and maintaining an open future where people have agency.</p> <p>This narrative summarizes our discussion about your TSoI, "uncertainties of the future of work." Does this accurately reflect your thinking so far? Would you like to make any amendments or additions to this narrative?</p>
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Illustration of procedural questions for scaffolding Relational Movements	
User	Can you please help me by scaffolding relational movements
AI/Claude	<p>Certainly! I'd be happy to help you scaffold relational movements to further enhance the complexity of your thinking about the uncertainties in the future of work, particularly focusing on the impact of climate change. We'll use the instructions from the CT_CODING_SC.RL.RM_SCAFFOLDING RELATIONAL MOVEMENTS PROTOCOL to guide this process.</p> <p>Let's begin with [PHASE 0] to clarify procedures and language.</p> <p>[SC.REL.RM.PQ.Q1] I would like to invite you to explore a wider number and type of potential relations between the bits of information and the different dimensions and sub-dimensions for the description of your TSoI. Are there relations that you particularly would like to explore and for which I could provide you with relational movements scaffolding questions? If so, we will start with those relations and later on I will propose we explore relations randomly. How would you like to proceed?</p> <p>[SC.REL.RM.PQ.Q2] I will call each bit of information or dimension that we will consider to explore in a relational way, a "relatum" or "relata" (plural). It means an information entity that has an inherent relational nature and is better understood in the context of other information or dimensions. Can we proceed?</p> <p>[SC.REL.RM.PQ.Q3] As I pose the questions, I will invite you to pay attention to what ideas come to your mind and to the potential relevance of the relations explored. Try to "think with your whole body" and pay attention to your reactions. If when making a relational movement another dimension comes to mind, or interesting or novel information (e.g., hypotheses) or ideas, let me know so that I can make a note. You just need to ask me to add a note to a mental map. I can also record those ideas as</p>

	<p>Relational Movement Ideas and maybe guide new relational movements from there. I will number and visually map the Relational Movement ideas in the Relational Map we are creating. Once you feel that you have a truly emergent idea (a new hypothesis, an insight) or something that comes to mind that you feel might be important and that is not simply reduced to the relata, I can add it to the map, mark it and number it as an Emergent Idea. That way we can later see the relations we built, with the emergent ideas and to the base ideas, to test its fitness. Can we proceed?</p> <p>Please let me know if you're comfortable with these procedures, and we can then move on to exploring relational movements.</p>
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Illustration of a selection and adaptation of a Scaffolding Question for the property of Relationality/Relational Movements	
<p>AI/Claude</p>	<p>Thank you for that insightful response. You've highlighted the complex, circular nature of the relationship between climate change and work patterns, especially in agriculture. This circular perspective is particularly interesting. Let's explore this further:</p> <p>[SC.REL.RM.SCAFF.Q7] How does time determine or affect the nature of the relation between these relata? How are these relata related temporally (e.g., co-exist, one follows the other, have different rhythms, there is recursion, etc)?</p> <p>Consider how the relationship between climate change impacts and work patterns/industries might evolve over different time scales. Think about immediate responses, medium-term adaptations, and long-term transformations. How might these temporal aspects influence each other?</p>

Illustrative excerpts for Case 4: ext.user#2

Illustration of a selection and adaptation of a Scaffolding Question for the property of Structural Variety and Dimensionality	
<p>AI/Claude</p>	<p>Thank you for your thoughtful response, B. You've identified several important additional elements in the system of nature-based solutions (NBS). Let's build on this to deepen our understanding.</p> <p>Based on the elements you've identified, let's explore how they're organized within the system:</p> <p>[SC.SVD.MD.IC.2.SCAFFQ2] How are these elements (political structures, economic factors, social effects, and cultural diversity) internally arranged in relation to each other in the context of NBS? Are</p>

	<p>there hierarchies or distinct levels of organization among them?</p> <p>Take your time to consider this question. Your response will help us understand the structural complexity of the sociopolitical dimension of NBS.</p>
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Illustrative excerpts for Case 5: ext.user#3

Illustration of a Dialogical Scaffolding followed by Synthesis	
AI/Claude	[SC.SVD.MD.E.FQ2] Could you provide a description of the social, material, cultural, institutional and natural environment of the ‘love family’? For example, what is the neighbourhood like where they live, what community resources do they have available, or what environmental challenges do they face?
User	<p>the housing conditions are quite precarious in structural terms, but the mother takes care of the space in a very brave and careful way, transforming it into a home. the context is somewhat challenging, in that it is mostly precarious and inhabited by families with low resources and other associated problems, which sometimes lead to conflicts. One of the family's main aims is to move out of the house, but financial conditions haven't allowed them to do so. They have already tried to find other solutions through social housing, but there has not yet been a positive response. Despite these conditions, the area has good sports and leisure facilities as well as easy access to the transport network and other services.</p>
AI/Claude	<p>Thank you for this detailed description of the Amor ‘family’ environment. This information adds important layers to our understanding of the system. I will synthesise and organise this new information:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Housing conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Structurally precarious ● Mum transforms the space into a home through meticulous care ● Strong desire to move to better housing 2. Social context: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mostly precarious neighbourhood ● Neighbourhood with low-income families ● Occasional conflicts in the community 3. Economic conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited financial resources ● Difficulty in moving to better housing ● Active search for solutions through social housing (unsuccessful so far) 4. Community infrastructure and resources:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Good sports and leisure facilities ● Easy access to transport network ● Proximity to other services <p>5. Resilience and adaptation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mother's ability to create a cosy environment despite structural limitations <p>This description of the environment significantly enriches our understanding of the 'Amor' family, showing how external factors influence its dynamics and well-being.</p> <p>To continue developing a complex understanding, I'll ask the next fundamental question:</p> <p>[SC.SVD.MD.O.FQ3] Please provide a description of yourselves as observers who are thinking about and interacting with the 'love family'. Do you consider yourself to be part of, in contact with, or outside the 'love family'?</p>
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Illustration of Narrative Mode	
User	<p>please enter narrative mode and offer me a TSoI_NARRATIVE</p> <p>(Note: The chat took place in Portuguese. All text was translated from Portuguese to English. Translated was performed with DeepL.com (free version))</p>
AI/Claude	<p>Certainly. I'll go into narrative mode and offer you a TSoI_NARRATIVE based on all the information you've shared so far.</p> <p>(Note: the user defined its TSoI as a family case, they called Family Amor, which means Love).</p> <p>[ARTIFACT]</p> <p># TSoI_NARRATIVE: The Story of the Amor Family</p> <p>In the heart of a challenging neighbourhood, where economic and social difficulties are a constant, we find the Amor Family. This single-parent family, made up of a resilient mum and her 11-year-old son, is like a whirlwind that moves love around, facing adverse winds, but always in search of light.</p> <p>The mother, marked by a history of parental rejection and an accident that left visible scars, carries deep insecurities. However, she has transformed these painful experiences into a fierce and protective love for her son. Her life revolves around him, creating a cosy home even in precarious housing conditions. She keeps everything impeccably clean, as if external order could compensate for the internal chaos that sometimes plagues her.</p> <p>Her son, a docile and polite boy, navigates between the role of child and confidant. Well integrated at school, he bears the brunt of his mother's worries, secretly wishing she could relax a little more. The recent change of school cycle has brought his mother's anxieties to the surface,</p>

	<p>threatening the autonomy and self-confidence the boy has been building.</p> <p>The father, although he doesn't live with them, is a constant presence. His more permissive parenting style contrasts with the mother's authoritarian approach, creating a complex dynamic. Both parents, however, share a deep love for their son, each expressing it in their own way.</p> <p>The family lives in a delicate balance, like an isolated microcosm in the midst of a larger community. Their social circle is small, limited to a few close family members and trusted friends. This reduced social network, together with limited access to information, creates a protective but also isolating bubble.</p> <p>In this scenario, the support team emerges as a vital bridge. You are more than observers; you are active participants in this family system. Your presence brings not only practical support, but also a connection with the outside world, mediating tensions and opening up possibilities.</p> <p>The Amor Family is a testimony to resilience and unconditional love. Each day is a delicate dance between protection and the need for growth, between the desire for stability and the inevitability of change. Like the whirling wind that symbolises their journey, they continue to spin, facing challenges but always seeking the light of love and hope.</p> <p>The future of the Amor Family remains uncertain, but full of potential. With the continued support and empathetic understanding you offer, there is hope that they can find a healthier balance. The challenge lies in helping the mother loosen the reins a little, allowing her son to grow in autonomy, while strengthening the support network around them.</p> <p>Ultimately, the story of Familia Amor is a powerful reminder of the complexity of human relationships and the resilience of the human spirit. It's a story still in development, with many chapters yet to be written, where every small step towards growth and stability is a victory to be celebrated.</p> <p>~~~~~</p> <p>This TSoI_NARRATIVE narrative offers a holistic and contextualised view of the Amor Family, integrating the various elements and dynamics we've discussed so far. It captures the complexity of family relationships, the impact of the environment, and your role as a support team.</p> <p>Some key points that emerge from this narrative:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The family's resilience in the face of multiple challenges. 2. The complex dynamic between protection and the need for autonomy. 3. The impact of social and informational isolation. 4. The importance of your role as a bridge between the family and the outside world. 5. The potential for growth and positive change, despite the difficulties. <p>This narrative can serve as a reference point for future reflection and to guide your interventions. It can also be updated as new information and developments emerge.</p> <p>Would you like to make any changes or additions to this narrative? Or would you prefer us to continue exploring different perspectives on the</p>
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	family, as suggested in the previous question?
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Illustration of the MAPPING Mode combined with METAPHOR MODE

User	Can you please make an updated version of the TSoI map?
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AI/Claude	Of course. I'm going to create an updated version of the TSoI (Target System of Interest) map for the 'Amor' family, incorporating the new insights and the metaphor of the paradise island that we developed [ARTIFACT]
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This updated TSoI map integrates the paradise island metaphor with the factual elements of the 'love family' case. Here is an explanation of the elements:

1. island (centre): represents the 'love family' as a whole.
2. Beach (edge of island): Symbolises the mother as the interface between the family and the outside world. The wavy shape represents the protective and sometimes turbulent nature of this interface.
3. Vegetation (centre of the island): Represents the son, well adapted but vulnerable to changes in the environment.

	<p>4. Sun: Symbolises the father, a constant but distant presence, influencing the ‘island’ on a regular basis.</p> <p>5. Ocean (background): Represents the wider social and material environment in which the family is inserted.</p> <p>6. Clouds: Symbolise the challenges faced by the family.</p> <p>7. Boats: Represent the different institutions involved (school, health, social action), each with its own perspective and approach.</p> <p>8. Lighthouse: Symbolises B.'s team, offering guidance and support.</p> <p>9. Connecting lines: These show the interactions between the family and the different elements of the system.</p> <p>This visual map helps us to see:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The centrality of the family in the system 2. The multiple influences and stakeholders involved 3. The complexity of the relationships between the different elements 4. The crucial role of the mother as the ‘interface’ of the family 5. The unique position of the Neighbourhood Team as a source of guidance <p>This visual representation captures the complexity of the system in a way that can reveal new perspectives or areas of potential intervention.</p> <p>Are there any elements you would like to add, remove or modify in this updated map? Does this visualisation help identify new areas for exploration or intervention?</p>
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Illustrative excerpts for Case 6: ext.user#4

Illustration of a Synthesis following Dialogical Scaffolding for the property of Relationality/Relations as Entities	
AI/Claude	Case Relationship Dynamics Map

The diagram illustrates the relationships in Case. At the top left, a box titled 'Efeitos' (Effects) lists outcomes for two scenarios: 'Quando há conflito A+P' (When there is conflict A+P) and 'Quando há harmonia' (When there is harmony). The conflict scenario lists: 'Menor capacidade parental' (Lower parental capacity), 'Menor disponibilidade para intervenção' (Lower availability for intervention), and 'Reatividade aumentada' (Increased reactivity). The harmony scenario lists: 'Maior disponibilidade para mudança' (Higher availability for change) and 'Melhor funcionamento do sistema' (Better system functioning). The main diagram shows 'Andrea' at the center, connected to 'Pais/Avós' (Parents/Guardians) and 'Crianças' (Children). 'Pais/Avós' is connected to 'Crianças' via 'Cuidados/Suporte' (Care/Support). 'Andrea' is connected to 'Crianças' via 'Influenciada pelo estado emocional' (Influenced by emotional state) and 'Oscila entre fusão e afastamento' (Oscillates between fusion and distancing). 'Andrea' is connected to 'CAFAP' (Family Assessment and Support Program) via 'Produção informação/Apoio' (Production of information/Support) and 'Decisões' (Decisions). 'CAFAP' is connected to 'CPCJ' (Child Protection Court) via 'Informação' (Information). 'Pais/Avós' is connected to 'CAFAP' via 'Relação pouco clara' (Unclear relationship) and 'Influência inexplorada' (Unexplored influence). 'Crianças' is connected to 'CPCJ' via 'Informação' (Information). There are also dotted lines representing unexplored relationships between 'Pais/Avós' and 'Crianças', and between 'Pais/Avós' and 'CAFAP'.

[PHASE 1 - STEP 1.1 Continuing]
 I've created a visual representation of the relationships in Case, showing:
 Core relationships between Andrea, her parents, and the children

- Institutional relationships with CAFAP and CPCJ
- Unexplored relationships (dotted lines)
- Key effects of relationship dynamics

Would you like me to continue with the previous question about how these relationships affect individual elements, or would you prefer to discuss what you observe in this visualization?

Illustrative example of a scaffolding modulating question on the property of Relationality/Relations as Entities

<p>User</p>	<p>We realise that the children are affected by the dynamics related to Andrea and her parents, we don't know if they are afraid, but we imagine that they are, because they are sheltered by the impact of these relationships. Children are most strongly affected by relational patterns. When the interaction is negative, Andrea no longer feels competent.</p>
	<p>[PHASE 1 - STEP 1.1 Continuing] Thank you for those important remarks. Let's explore the last fundamental question of this series: [SC.RL.R.F.Q11] How can we continue to explore and update our understanding of relationships within the Case? Specifically: What methods can we use to track and analyse changes in relationships over time? How can we monitor the impact of these relationships on the children? How can we assess the development of Andrea's parenting skills in relation to these dynamics?</p>

AI/Claude	Can you give us suggestions for that understanding of relations with the case?
AI/Claude	<p>[PHASE 1 - STEP 1.2] Before offering suggestions, let's explore a different dimension of relationships through a modulating question:</p> <p>[SC.RL.R.MOD.SV.Q1] How do the relationships in Case change when we consider different contexts or environments? For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are relationships like at home vs. in the context of CAFAP? • How do dynamics vary in times of stress vs. times of calm? • What contextual factors seem to most influence the nature and strength of these relationships? <p>Once we've explored this, I'll be able to offer more specific suggestions for understanding</p> <p>Note: This text was translated from Portuguese to English</p>

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